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5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Description		
API	Application Programming Interface	IWL	Interworking Layer
BLUO	Browse-and-Lookup, Uploading and Onboarding	JPA	Java Persistency API
CB	Context Blueprint	JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
CD	Context Descriptor	KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CPU	Core Processing Unit	MANO	Management and Orchestration
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete	MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets	MSO	Multi-Site Orchestrator
CtxB	Context Blueprint	MMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication
DB	Database	NBI	North Bound Interface
DCM	Data Collection Manager	NFV	Network Function Virtualization
DCS	Data Collection and Storage	NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
DF	Deployment Flavour	NSD	Network Service Descriptor
E2E	End to End	PNF	Physical Network Function
EBB	Experiment Blueprint Builder	RBAC	Role Based Access Control
EEM	Experiment Execution Manager	REST	REpresentational State Transfer
ELM	Experiment Lifecycle Manager	SLA	Service Level Agreement
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile BroadBand	SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol
EPC	Evolved Packet Core	TCB	Test Case Blueprint
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standard Institute	TSB	Ticketing System Backend
ExpB	Experiment Blueprint	URL	Uniform Resource Locator
ExpD	Experiment Descriptor	URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication
GUI	Graphical User Interface	VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
HTML	Hyper Text Markup Language	VM	Virtual Machine
HTTP	Hyper Text Transfer Protocol	VNF	Virtual Network Function
IBN	Intent Based Networking	VNFD	Virtual Network Function Descriptor
IBNS	Intent Based Networking System	VNFFG	Virtual Network Function Forwarding Graph
ID	Identifier	VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
IAM	Identity and Access Manager	VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
IDMS	Intent Driven Management System	WP	Work Package
IL	Instantiation Level	YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

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Executive Summary

This document presents the final version of the 5G EVE experimental Portal. It describes all services originally included in the 5G EVE project proposal, and some services requested during the project lifetime by other work packages in 5G EVE as well as other European projects like the 5G-SOLUTIONS, which will use the 5G EVE platform.

This deliverable is useful for all verticals planning to use the new functionalities delivered in the last months of the 5G EVE project, as the full REST API to access all available services is included, as well as the extensions implemented on the graphical user interface to perform all experimentation phases defined by the 5G EVE project.

Finally, the full 5G EVE user guide is included as an annex, so all users of the 5G EVE platform have a single document with all the information to access the main services of the platform. Note that this user guide will be made public, including the information to use functionalities provided by other work packages of the 5G EVE project, such as the diagnosis and validation tools.

1 Introduction

This document presents the final version of the 5G EVE Portal, where we include the full REST API to access all services provided by the 5G EVE end-to-end platform, the internal REST API used to provide services to internal components of the 5G EVE Portal and the final user manual to iterate with the Portal, in the annex.

New functionalities of the 5G EVE Portal have been validated using a private development environment, which was provided by partners of the 5G EVE project involved in work package 4. This validation was performed by executing 5G EVE internal use cases, like the Spanish Industry 4.0 use case, and some simple ad-hoc use cases, designed for each specific validation. After extensive trials, new services were integrated in the production environment, which is publicly available to all users of the 5G EVE platform at <https://portal.5g-eve.eu>. Currently, the public environment offers all services originally planned in the project proposal and new features that will be described next.

Compared with the functionalities provided by the second version of the 5G EVE Portal, already presented in deliverable D4.4 [1], this final version includes the following new services: (1) capability to deploy multi-site experiments in different sites, and (2) an extension to the public REST API to allow 5G EVE platform users to access the published metrics in real time. The former functionality has required some modifications to the 5G EVE information model to include one new blueprint (the inter-site blueprint) and modifications to the NSD to include the capacity of describing nested services. Furthermore, these changes required modifications to the graphical user interface. The latter functionality has implied the development of new end points to the REST API provided by the Data Collection and Storage component, which in turn has required to implement new internal functions between components. All these changes are documented in sections 1 and 2, while the new version of the user manual presented in the annex of this document includes all the necessary steps to use these new services. Furthermore, the OpenAPIs of all components defined and implemented by the 5G EVE project can be found in the public GitHub of the project: <https://github.com/5GEVE/OpenAPI>

It is important to highlight that, while the multi-site functionality was included in the scope of 5G EVE project, the access to the monitoring information in real time functionality is a not originally planned service feature developed as a response to the feedback provided by other projects willing to further automate their own experiments with 5G EVE platform support.

2 Experimental 5G EVE Portal

The 5G EVE portal is the entry point to all services provided by the 5G EVE infrastructure. Users (experimenters, experiment developers, VNF providers, verticals, site manager and site administrators, as defined by the 5G EVE project [3]) can access all the functionalities of the 5G EVE infrastructure using a graphical user interface or some functionalities, declared next in this section, through the REST API. The portal architecture is composed by components in the backend and components for the graphical user interface (GUI), as defined in [3]. Section 2.1 includes the final version of the former components while section 2.2 shows the main changes of the GUI, since the last version of the Portal documented in [1]. Finally, section 2.3 presents the final 5G EVE information model, which includes tables with the information model of all Blueprints defined in the project.

2.1 Portal backend components

2.1.1 Role-Based Access Control

The Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) is the component responsible to provide user management and authentication/authorization to other modules. This component relies on Keycloak¹, which is an Identity and Access Management service (IAM) to store users, generate and renew authentication artefacts that belong to each user. RBAC exposes a REST API to other components, like front-end application and for other back-end components that might need it, thus avoiding HTTP redirections.

2.1.1.1 Role-Based Access Control Interface (Irbac)

This section presents the REST API offered by the RBAC to other components, and to external users too. Table 1 shows the summary of all endpoints provided by the RBAC, including the type of the method, the URI, a short description of the endpoint and if the endpoint is public or private. Every endpoint is then presented in detail in next tables, from Table 2 to Table 11, including the format of the requests and the replies, as well as the resulting codes, both for success and errors.

Table 1: Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) REST API

HTTP method	URI	Description	Public
POST	/portal/rbac/register	Endpoint to create a new user at the portal.	Yes
POST	/portal/rbac/login	Allows the creation of a new session for a specific user who is already registered at the portal.	Yes
POST	/portal/rbac/refresh token	Allows users to obtain a new access token once the one they have expired.	Yes
GET	/portal/rbac/logout	Closes a user session.	Yes
GET	/portal/rbac/extra/use-cases	Enables the retrieval of use cases associated to a specific user.	Yes
POST	/portal/rbac/extra/use-cases	Allows the addition of new use cases to a specific user.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/rbac/extra/use-cases	Enables the removal of use cases associated to a specific user.	Yes
GET	/portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites	Allows the retrieval of sites managed by a specific user.	Yes
POST	/portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites	Enables the addition of sites managed by a specific user.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites	Enables the removal of sites managed by a specific user.	Yes

¹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Table 2: REST API - POST /portal/rbac/register

POST /portal/rbac/register			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request Body (JSON)	email	String	Email address of the new user
	username	String	Username of the new user
	firstName	String	First Name of the new user
	lastName	String	Last Name of the new user
	password	String	Password
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 3: REST API - POST /portal/rbac/login

POST /portal/rbac/login			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request Body (JSON)	email	String	Email address of the new user
	password	String	Password
Response body	access_token	String	Access token to include in all the requests for resources
	refresh_token	String	Refresh token that allows access token renewal
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 4: REST API - POST /portal/rbac/refresh_token

POST /portal/rbac/refresh_token			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request Body (JSON)	refresh_token	String	Refresh token to generate a new access token
Response body	access_token	String	Access token to include in all the requests for resources
	refresh_token	String	Refresh token that allows access token renewal
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 5: REST API - GET /portal/rbac/logout

GET /portal/rbac/logout			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: bearer + access token	String	Header that stores the access token of the user
Request Body (JSON)	--	--	--
Response body	--	--	--
	--	--	--

Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 500 INTERNAL ERROR

Table 6: REST API - GET /portal/rbac/extra/use-cases

GET /portal/rbac/extra/use-cases			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: bearer + access token	String	Header that stores the access token of the user
Request Body (JSON)	--	--	--
Response body (JSON)	details	Array<String>	Use cases associated to the user
	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 7: REST API - POST /portal/rbac/extra/use-cases

POST /portal/rbac/extra/use-cases			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: bearer + access token	String	Header that stores the access token of the user
Request Body (JSON)	use_cases	Array<String>	List of use cases to be added to the user
Response body (JSON)	--	--	--
	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 8: REST API - DELETE /portal/rbac/extra/use-cases

DELETE /portal/rbac/extra/use-cases			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: bearer + access token	String	Header that stores the access token of the user
Request Body (JSON)	use_cases	Array<String>	List of use cases to be removed
Response body	--	--	--
	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 9: REST API - GET /portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites

GET /portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: bearer + access token	String	Header that stores the access token of the user
Request Body (JSON)	--	--	--
	details	Array<String>	Sites managed by the specific user

Response body (JSON)	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 10: REST API - POST/portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites

POST /portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: bearer + access token	String	Header that stores the access token of the user
Request Body (JSON)	managed_sites	Array<String>	List of sites to be added at the managed sites list of the user
Response body (JSON)	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 11: REST API - DELETE /portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites

DELETE /portal/rbac/extra/managed-sites			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: bearer + access token	String	Header that stores the access token of the user
Request Body (JSON)	managed_sites	Array<String>	List of sites to be removed from the managed sites list associated to the user
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

2.1.1.2 Implementation updates

This component was not updated since the last version of the 5G EVE Portal, and the last implementation details can be found in D4.4 [1].

2.1.2 Experiment Lifecycle Manager

2.1.2.1 Experiment Lifecycle Manager Interface (Ielm)

The Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) is the component of the Portal Backend responsible for management of the experiment lifecycle and for the processing of the different actions which can be performed on experiments. The component offers a REST-based north-bound interface that is used by the 5GEVE Portal GUI and by other external REST clients to trigger the desired operation via an open API. The ELM follows the role-based authorization scheme established in D4.1 [2], and therefore all the incoming requests are authenticated and authorized through the RBAC component described in section 2.1. In terms of updates there were three main functionalities introduced by this new release: (i) Support for multi-site experiments; (ii) Support for RAN slice parameters; (iii) Support for experiment execution performance diagnostics.

Table 12 reports all the actions that can be performed through the Experiment Lifecycle Manager NBI, while the rest of the tables in this section detail the parameters used for each operation and the expected responses.

The full specification of the REST-based API is available in OpenAPI format in <https://github.com/nextworks-it/experiment-portal/blob/master/API/ExperimentLifecycleManager.json>

Table 12: Experiment Lifecycle Manager REST API

HTTP method	URI	Description	Public
POST	/portal/elm/experiment	Creates a new experiment.	Yes
GET	/portal/elm/experiment<?[filter_parameters]>	Returns a list of experiments matching a given filter, i.e. based on the experiment identifier or the experiment descriptor identifier. The acceptable filter_parameters are the following: <Exp ID; ExpD ID>.	Yes
PUT	/portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/status	Changes the status of an experiment. The permitted changes are the following: - from scheduling to accepted - from scheduling to refused - from accepted to ready	No
POST	/portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/deploy	Deploys the virtual environment to run the experiment (i.e. instantiates the associated NFV network service). The experiment must be in ready state.	Yes
POST	/portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/execute	Executes of one or more tests for a given experiment. The experiment must be in instantiated state.	Yes
POST	/portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/terminate	Terminates the virtual environment where the experiment has been executed (i.e. terminates the associated NFV network service). The experiment must be in instantiated state.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/elm/experiment/{expId}	Removes an experiment and its record from the system. The experiment must be in refused, terminated or failed state.	Yes

Table 13: REST API - POST /portal/elm/experiment

POST /portal/elm/experiment			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	experimentName	String	Name of the experiment instance.
	experimentDescriptorId	String	ID of the experiment descriptor defining the characteristics of the experiment to be created.
	proposedTimeSlot	ExperimentExecutionTimeslot	Definition of the timeslot proposed for the execution of the experiment. Includes startTime and endTime.
	targetSites	List<EveSite>	List of sites where the experiment must be instantiated and executed.
	useCase	String	Use case associated to the experiment.
Response body	experimentId	String	ID of the created experiment.
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED			

Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR

Table 14: REST API - GET /portal/elm/experiment<?[filter_parameters]>

GET /portal/elm/experiment<?[filter_parameters]>			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
URI Query Parameters	expId	String	ID of the requested experiment.
	expDId	String	ID of the experiment descriptor associated to the requested experiments.
Response body	experiments	List<Experiment>	Information about the requested experiments, including their results if available.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 15: REST API - PUT /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/status

PUT /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/status			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	status	Enum	New status of the experiment.
URI Variables	expId	String	ID of the experiment to be updated.
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 202 ACCEPTED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 16: REST API - POST /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/deploy

POST /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/deploy			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	expId	String	ID of the experiment to be deployed.
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 202 ACCEPTED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 17: REST API - POST /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/execute

POST /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/execute			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	executionName	String	Name of the requested execution.
	testCaseDescriptor-Configuration	Map<String, Map<String, String>>	Specification of the test cases to be executed and their user configuration. The key of the outer map

			is the testCaseDescriptorId. The value is an inner map with the user parameters for that test cases. The test cases and the user parameters specified in the request override the ones defined in the experiment descriptor. If this field is empty, all the test cases defined in the experiment descriptor are executed by default.
	perfDiag	Boolean	Indicates if the experiment execution will be subject of performance diagnostics by the Diagnostics tool
URI Variables	expId	String	ID of the experiment to be executed.
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 202 ACCEPTED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 18: REST API - POST /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/terminate

POST /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}/action/terminate			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	expId	String	ID of the experiment to be terminated.
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 202 ACCEPTED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 19: REST API - DELETE /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}

DELETE /portal/elm/experiment/{expId}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
URI Variables	expId	String	ID of the experiment to be deleted.
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

2.1.2.2 Implementation updates

As established in D4.2 [3] the ELM is a Spring-boot application, which relays on Apache Maven’s [7] building tool, PostgreSQL [8] as backend database and RabbitMQ [9] as internal bus for the exchange of asynchronous messages among the ELM internal components. Figure 1 shows the high-level architecture of the ELM, highlighting in red the components which were updated in this final release. We refer to D4.2 for the details about the different components and the internal workflows of the ELM.

The “ELM REST controller” module parses and performs an initial validation of the incoming REST requests, interacting with the RBAC module and the Keycloak system for the authentication and authorization of the requests. The actual processing of the different operations is performed by the “ELM engine”, which manages the experiment instances creating the Experiment Instances Manager which will be responsible of the lifecycle of each particular experiment. The experiment information and status are stored in a PostgreSQL database using JPA repositories, for persistency reasons. In the Southbound, the ELM uses a driver-based approach to interact with other components of the 5G EVE platform (namely, the Ticketing system, the Data Collection and Storage, the Experiment Execution Manager, the IWL Multi-Site Network Orchestrator (MSNO) and the Portal Catalogue). Each service is configured with a specific REST based driver which allows to decouple the driver specific logic.

Figure 1: ELM high-level architecture and updates

As mentioned before, three main functionalities have been introduced in this new release:

- Support for multi-site experiments, for managing the instantiation of experiments across multiple 5G EVE facilities.
- Support for RAN slice parameters, for defining the specific RAN requirements of the services associated to the experiments.
- Support for experiment execution performance diagnostics, to enable the procedures for the post-execution analysis and diagnostics of the experiment results (performed by the Diagnostics tools developed in WP5).

These new functionalities have been implemented through enhancement of the ELM REST Controller, Experiment Instance Manager, IWL MSNO Service and Portal Catalogue Service:

- **ELM REST Controller**, updated to handle the experiment run execution requests to enable the diagnostic tool analysis;

- **Experiment Instance Manager**, updated to handle the lifecycle management of multi-site experiments and the extended information models and interfaces towards the Southbound plugins in terms of: RAN parameters and multi-site network service placement constraints;
- **IWL MSNO Service**, in multi-site experiment scenarios the IWL MSNO deploys one end-to-end network service (NS) composed by nested NS which are deployed in the 5G EVE sites of the experiment. Since the particular site where each nested NS should run is determined in the 5G EVE Portal during the experiment definition phase, the NS Instantiation Request issued from the ELM has been updated in order to be able to encode the site in which each nested NS has to be deployed. In particular the *target-site* parameter of the *additionalParamsForNs* follows the format *nestedNsdA:siteA/nestedNsdB:siteB* for multi-site experiment deployment. We refer to section 2.1.5 for further details regarding the multi-site experiment definition. For the support of RAN Slice parameters, this module was also updated to extend the *SapData* with the inclusion of a *RadioSliceProfile* (which is defined in the experiment descriptor provided during the experiment customization phase);
- **Portal Catalogue Service**: The multi-site experiment support required to update the translator functionality and interfaces of the 5G EVE Portal Catalogue in order to be able to determine the specific NS, deployment flavour and instantiation level to be instantiated in each site depending on the experiment parameters determined in the experiment descriptor provided during the experiment customization phase. On the ELM side the client libraries were updated to reflect this update. In particular the *nestedVsTranslation* parameter was added to the translator response, which is a map containing the translation for each component of the end-to-end vertical service blueprint (VSB).

2.1.3 Data Collection and Storage

As stated in D4.4 [1], the Data Collection and Storage component (DCS) placed in the Portal backend is one of the components that belongs to the Experiment monitoring and Maintenance & Results Collection toolchain, already presented in D4.1 [2]. Two different tools can be distinguished:

- The data collection, aggregation and pre-processing tool, which collects the experiment results, metrics (both infrastructure and application metrics) and KPIs generated for a given experiment provided by the Data Collection Manager component from the I/W Framework;
- The data indexing and storage tool, which enables the capability of searching and filtering among all the data gathered by the data collection tool for obtaining the useful information that will be displayed afterwards in the Portal GUI, also providing data persistence.

2.1.3.1 Data Collection and Storage Interface (Idcs)

The Data Collection and Storage interface, compared to the version delivered in D4.4 [1], has been extended with the definition of two new endpoints that can be used to retrieve the monitoring data saved in Elasticsearch. The rest of endpoints are the same.

These operations that can be handled by other components in the Portal architecture will be related only to the following functionalities offered by the DCS:

- The management of Kibana dashboards;
- The retrieval of monitoring data from Elasticsearch;
- The management of the signalling topics.

The two first functionalities are enabled by a specific Java application embedded in the DCS, and the last one, as it is simpler, will be provided with a simple Python application implementing Flask. This architecture will be further explained in Section 0. The updated REST API exposed by the DCS is presented in the following Table 20:

Table 20: Data Collection and Storage REST API

HTTP method	URI	Description	Public
-------------	-----	-------------	--------

POST	/portal/dcs/dashboard	Create the Kibana dashboards for the metrics and/or KPIs provided in the request.	No
GET	/portal/dcs/dashboard/{experimentId}	Retrieve the Kibana dashboards' URLs already created for the metrics and/or KPIs related to the {experimentId} experiment.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/dcs/dashboard	Delete the Kibana dashboards for the metrics and/or KPIs provided in the request.	No
GET	/portal/dcs/topics/{experimentId}	Retrieve the topics associated to a given {experimentId}.	Yes
GET	/portal/dcs/topics/{experimentId}/{topic}	Retrieve the monitoring data collected for a given {topic} from a specific {experimentId}.	Yes
POST	/portal/dcs/start_signalling	Enable the signalling topics. Internal operation.	No
DELETE	/portal/dcs/stop_signalling	Disable the signalling topics. Internal operation.	No

The specification of the REST APIs for interacting with both functionalities can be checked in their GitHub repositories: <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-kibana-dashboards-handler> (tag v0.2) for the Kibana dashboards' and Elasticsearch data's handler, and <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-signalling-topic-handler> (tag v0.2) for the signalling topics' handler. Tables from Table 21 to Table 27 present a summary of those endpoints offered by the DCS component, including the parameters required in the request messages and the information included in the response. Every table includes the resulting (either success or error) code too.

Table 21: REST API - POST /portal/dcs/dashboard

POST /portal/dcs/dashboard			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	dcsRequestWrapper	DcsRequestWrapper	It provides a list of RecordWrapper, where each RecordWrapper contains a single ValueWrapper that represents the data related to the metric or KPI whose dashboard will be created afterwards. This format is the same as the message sent from the ELM to the DCM ² .
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK.			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST.			

Table 22: REST API - GET /portal/dcs/dashboard/{experimentId}

GET /portal/dcs/dashboard/{experimentId}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--

² Example of these messages were described in D4.4 [1], Annex A.

URI Variables	experimentId	String	Value of the experimentId from which the metrics' and KPIs' dashboards will be obtained.
Response body	dashboardWrapper	DashboardWrapper	It contains a parameter called urls, a List<UrlWrapper> where the UrlWrapper contains a String with the url of a metric/KPI.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK.			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST.			

Table 23: REST API - DELETE /portal/dcs/dashboard

DELETE /portal/dcs/dashboard			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	dcsRequestWrapper	DcsRequestWrapper	The same as in the POST request.
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 200 ACCEPTED.			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST.			

Table 24: REST API - GET /portal/dcs/topics/{experimentId}

GET /portal/dcs/topics/{experimentId}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: Bearer <access_token>	String	Header that stores the <access_token> of the user.
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	experimentId	String	Value of the experimentId from which the metrics' and KPIs' values will be obtained.
Response body	topicsWrapper	TopicsWrapper	It contains a parameter called topics, a List<TopicWrapper> where the TopicWrapper contains a String with the topic name.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK.			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST.			

Table 25: REST API - GET /portal/dcs/topics/{experimentId}/{topic}

GET /portal/dcs/topics/{experimentId}/{topic}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Authentication Headers	Authorization: Bearer <access_token>	String	Header that stores the <access_token> of the user.
Request body	elasticsearchParametersWrapper	ElasticsearchParametersWrapper	It contains two Integer values: "from" (database row from which the data will start to be retrieved – allowed values between 0 and 9.999), and "size" (number of

			records to be returned – allowed values between 1 and 10.000).
URI Variables	experimentId	String	Value of the experimentId from which the metrics’ and KPIs’ values will be obtained.
	topic	String	Topic from which the values will be obtained.
Response body	elasticsearchDcsResponseWrapper	ElasticsearchDcsResponseWrapper	It contains a parameter called data, a List<ElasticsearchDataWrapper> where the ElasticsearchDataWrapper contains the fields saved in Elasticsearch, according to the data model followed to send metrics’ and KPIs’ values in the Monitoring Platform. The fields are: “device_id” (String), “timestamp” (String), “unit” (String), “device_timestamp” ³ (String), “context” (String) and “value” (float).
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK.			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST.			

Table 26: REST API - POST /portal/dcs/start_signalling

POST /portal/dcs/start_signalling			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED.			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST.			

Table 27: REST API - DELETE /portal/dcs/stop_signalling

DELETE /portal/dcs/stop_signalling			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED.			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST.			

2.1.3.2 Implementation updates

³ The difference between “timestamp” and “device_timestamp” is that the first one is the timestamp generated by Logstash (i.e. the time in which the monitoring data has reached the Elastic Stack), whereas the second one is the timestamp generated by the Data Shipper (i.e. the time in which the monitoring data has been gathered by the Data Shipper).

The DCS architecture proposed in D4.4 [1] is the base of the final version of the DCS. In particular, Figure 2 updates that architecture by including minor changes, such as renaming both Python and Java logics with more meaningful names: DCS Handler⁴ and Dashboards' Handler⁵, respectively. Moreover, a link between the Dashboards' Handler and Elasticsearch has been provided, as that component is in charge of managing the monitoring data retrieval from Elasticsearch when requested via REST API. And finally, as this last version of the DCS fully implements the interaction with Keycloak (RBAC) for authentication purposes, a link between the Dashboards' Handler and the RBAC is also provided, in order to manage the authentication of the users that are requesting the data retrieval from Elasticsearch and also to retrieve the user names allowed to see a given dashboard.

Figure 2: Final DCS architecture

One aspect that has not been commented in previous deliverables is how Logstash manages the data received from Kafka in order to forward it to Elasticsearch. In particular, Logstash manages multiple pipelines (i.e. the Logstash data unit), where each pipeline has a one-to-one mapping with the Kafka topics created in the Data Collection Manager. As a result, the pipeline is composed by three parts: (1) the input, which is the Kafka topic (i.e. Logstash acts as a subscriber to that topic), (2) the filter, which parses the JSON received through Kafka and manipulates it for saving it in Elasticsearch (e.g. it changes data types of some fields, such as the timestamp, transforming into a Date), and (3) the output, which is an Elasticsearch index where the data will be saved, having again a one-to-one mapping between the Elasticsearch index and the Logstash pipeline (so, as a result, there is also a one-to-one mapping between the Elasticsearch index and the Kafka topic).

⁴ Software available here: <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-signalling-topic-handler> (v0.2 tag).

⁵ Software available here: <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-kibana-dashboards-handler> (v0.2 tag) and here: <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-kibana-dashboards-generator> (v0.1 tag).

Regarding the E2E workflow followed by the DCS Handler and the Dashboards' Handler, please refer to D4.4 [1], as there are no changes in that aspect. Moreover, for the low-level monitoring workflow, please refer to D3.5 [6], in the service description of the Data Collection Manager. However, the data model used for managing the Kibana dashboards in the Dashboards' Handler presents some small changes that can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Dashboards' Handler data model

In particular, both **Metric** and **Kpi** entities include now a field related to the `dashboardId` generated by Kibana and to the `kibanaUser` (a list of users separated by “,”) with permissions to see the dashboards. The last parameter is extracted thanks to the interaction between the DCS and the RBAC, retrieving the users that contains the `<use_case>` embedded in the topic name (which is the primary key in both **Metric** and **Kpi** entities) in the “`use_cases`” Keycloak attribute.

The deployment of the DCS, together with the DV, has been done with a specific Ansible playbook that configures an Ubuntu Server 16.04 LTS from scratch, provisioning all the packages, files and tools needed to integrate the Monitoring platform in 5G EVE. This Ansible playbook can be found here: <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-dv-deployment> (v0.2 tag).

2.1.4 File Storage

The File Storage component offers a service to other modules to upload large files, similar to a cloud storage system. The main user of this component is the VNF Storage module at the Portal GUI layer, which is used by VNF providers to upload VNF packages. Then, the involved site managers receive a ticket requesting the onboarding of the selected packages in their sites. Thus, the File Storage module after a successful uploading of a file, creates as many tickets as the sites selected by the VNF provider. These tickets should include the link to the uploaded package, so that site managers can download such file.

2.1.4.1 File Storage Interface (Ifs)

In the following we present all endpoints provided by the file storage component, where in Table 28 we show a summary of all endpoints, including the type of method, the URI suffix to call such method, a short description of the endpoint and if the method is public or not. All these endpoints are presented in detail in tables from Table 29 until Table 34, where in each table we show the required parameters used in a request, its type and a short description. Furthermore, these tables also include the expected response information and the code expected, both if the request has an error or if it is a success.

Table 28: File Storage REST API

HTTP method	URI	Description	Public
GET	/portal/fs/	Retrieves files associated to a user. If user has SiteManager role, he/she will retrieve all available files to be uploaded to their corresponding sites. It will return all files uploaded by the logged in user otherwise	Yes
POST	/portal/fs/upload/{filename}	Used to upload a single zip file and a list of one or more sites that have to be notified.	Yes
POST	/portal/fs/sites/{filename}	Allows the assignation of deployment sites to an already uploaded file	Yes
POST	/portal/fs/sites/{filename}	Used to update the status of an uploaded file at the site, allowing the site manager to notify the user as soon as the file is deployed	Yes
GET	/portal/fs/download/{filename}	Requests to download the file identified with a name.	Yes
POST	/portal/fs/delete/{filename}	Removes the upload notification created at during the uploading step.	Yes

Table 29: REST API - GET /portal/fs

GET /portal/fs/			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body	--	--	--
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 30: REST API - POST /portal/fs/upload/{filename}

POST /portal/fs/upload/{filename}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (form-data)	file	File	File to be uploaded
	--	--	--
URI Variables	filename	String	Name of the file to be uploaded
Response body (JSON)	details	String	Details of the operation
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED			

Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 404 NOT FOUND, 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 500 INTERNAL ERROR

Table 31: REST API - POST /portal/fs/sites/{filename}

POST /portal/fs/sites/{filename}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	sites	Array<String>	List of sites where the uploaded file should be deployed
URI Variables	filename	String	Name of the file that will be deployed on the different sites
Response body (JSON)	details	Array<String>	List of sites where deployment operation was correctly requested
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 404 NOT FOUND			

Table 32: REST API - POST /portal/fs/status/{filename}

POST /portal/fs/status/{filename}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	site	String	Site where the status of the file has changed
	status	String	Status at which the file should be updated at the specific site
URI Variables	filename	String	Name of the file
Response body (JSON)	details	String	Details of the operation
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			

Table 33: REST API - POST /portal/fs/download/{filename}

GET /portal/fs/download/{filename}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)			
URI Variables	filename	String	Name of the file
Response body (JSON)	details	String	Details of the operation
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 404 NOT FOUND			

Table 34: REST API - POST /portal/fs/delete/{filename}

POST /portal/fs/delete/{filename}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	site	String	Site where we want to remove the file
	--	--	--
URI Variables	filename	String	Name of the file

Response body (JSON)	details	String	Details of the operation
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 404 NOT FOUND			

2.1.4.2 Implementation updates

This component was not updated since the last version of the 5G EVE Portal, and the last implementation details can be found in D4.4 [1].

2.1.5 Catalogue Service

The Catalogue Service is the component of the Portal Backend responsible for management of the blueprints and descriptors required for the experiment design and definition (namely Vertical Service Blueprints (VSBs), Context Blueprints (CTXBs), Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (EXPBs and EXPDs respectively) as detailed in D4.1 [2]. Moreover, this module interacts with I/W framework catalogue to keep the synchronization between the blueprints and descriptors handled at the portal and I/W framework associated NFV descriptors handled at the I/W framework. This module offers an open API for the management and querying of the different descriptors. All the incoming requests are authenticated and authorized through the RBAC component described in section 2.1. In terms of updates there were two main functionalities introduced on this new release: (i) Support for multi-site experiments; (ii) Support for RAN slice parameters.

The full specification of the Catalogue Service is available in OpenAPI format in: <https://github.com/nextworks-it/slicer-catalogue/blob/5geve-release/API/EveBlueprintCatalogue.json>

2.1.5.1 Catalogue Service Interface (Ics)

As in previous sections, in this section we present the full list of endpoints offered by the catalogue service component. In Table 35 we summarize all endpoints, including the type of method for every endpoint, the URI suffix, a short description and the privacy or not of all endpoints. Finally, tables from Table 36 to Table 51 gives a detailed view of all these endpoints, which is useful to construct the proper request, as well as the expected result for each case.

Table 35: 5G-EVE Portal Catalogue REST API

HTTP method	URI	Description	Public
GET	/portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint	Get the list of the IDs of all the context blueprints matching available. If the filter is not specified, the IDs of all the existing context blueprints are returned.	Yes
POST	/portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint	Create and onboard a new context blueprint. The context blueprint is onboarded together with the associated NSD (if present in the request) and translation rules.	No
GET	/portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint/<id>	Get the details of the context blueprint with ID <id>.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint/<id>	Remove the context blueprint with ID <id>.	No
GET	/portal/catalogue/vsblueprint<?[filter_parameters]>	Get the list of the IDs of all the vertical service blueprints matching the filter criteria provided in the URI query parameters. If the filter is not specified, the IDs of all the existing vertical service blueprints are returned.	Yes

POST	/portal/catalogue/vsblueprint	Create and onboard a new vertical service blueprint. The vertical service blueprint is onboarded together with the associated NSD (if present in the request) and translation rules.	No
GET	/portal/catalogue/vsblueprint/<id>	Get the details of the vertical service blueprint with ID <id>.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/catalogue/vsblueprint/<id>	Remove the vertical service blueprint with ID <id>.	No
GET	/portal/catalogue/expblueprint<?[filter_parameters]>	Get the list of the IDs of all the experiment blueprints matching the filter criteria provided in the URI query parameters. If the filter is not specified, the IDs of all the existing experiment blueprints are returned.	Yes
POST	/portal/catalogue/expblueprint	Create and onboard a new experiment blueprint. The experiment blueprint is onboarded together with the associated NSD (if present in the request) and translation rules.	No
GET	/portal/catalogue/expblueprint/<id>	Get the details of the experiment blueprint with ID <id>.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/catalogue/expblueprint/<id>	Remove the experiment blueprint with ID <id>.	No
POST	/portal/catalogue/expdescriptor	Create and onboard a new experiment descriptor. All the associated VSD, CtxD and TCD are automatically created and onboarded.	Yes
GET	/portal/catalogue/expdescriptor	Get the details of all the experiment descriptors.	Yes
GET	/portal/catalogue/expdescriptor/<id>	Get the details of the experiment descriptor with ID <id>.	Yes
DELETE	/portal/catalogue/expdescriptor/<id>	Remove the experiment descriptor with ID <id>.	Yes

Table 36: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint

GET /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint<?[filter_parameters]>			
Response body	ctxBlueprintInfos	List<CtxBlueprintInfo>	List of context blueprint information elements available for the user
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 37: REST API - POST /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint

POST /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint			
Request body	ctxBlueprint	ContextBlueprint	Content of the context blueprint to be onboarded.
	nsds	List<Nsd>	NSD of the Network Services required to deploy the context execution elements.
	translationRules	List<TranslationRule>	Rules regulating the translation between a context descriptor based on the given blueprint and the associated network service.
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a

Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR

Table 38: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint/<id>

GET /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the queried context blueprint.
Response body	ctxBlueprintId	String	Unique ID of the context blueprint.
	version	String	Version of the context blueprint.
	name	String	Name of the context blueprint.
	ctxBlueprint	ContextBlueprint	Content of the context blueprint.
	onBoardedNsdInfoId	List<String>	IDs of the onboarded NSD associated to the given context blueprint.
	activeCtxdId	List<String>	IDs of the context descriptors associated to the given blueprint.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 39: REST API - DELETE /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint/<id>

DELETE /portal/catalogue/ctxblueprint/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the context blueprint to be deleted.
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 40: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint<?[filter_parameters]>

GET /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint<?[filter_parameters]>			
URI Query Parameters	Site	String	5G EVE site where the vertical service can be deployed
Response body	vsBlueprintInfo	List<VsBlueprintInfo>	List of vertical service blueprints information elements matching the filter provided in the URI Query parameters.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 41: REST API - POST /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint

POST /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint

Request body	vsBlueprint	VerticalServiceBlueprint	Content of the vertical service blueprint to be onboarded.
	nsds	List<Nsd>	NSD of the Network Services required to deploy the vertical service elements.
	translationRules	List<TranslationRule>	Rules regulating the translation between a vertical service descriptor based on the given blueprint and the associated network service.
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 42: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint/<id>

GET /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the queried vertical service blueprint.
Response body	vsBlueprintId	String	Unique ID of the vertical service blueprint.
	version	String	Version of the vertical service blueprint.
	name	String	Name of the vertical service blueprint.
	vsBlueprint	VerticalServiceBlueprint	Content of the vertical service blueprint.
	activeVsdId	List<String>	IDs of the vertical service descriptors associated to the given blueprint.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 43: REST API - DELETE /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint/<id>

DELETE /portal/catalogue/vsblueprint/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the vertical service blueprint to be deleted.
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 44: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/expblueprint<?[filter_parameters]>

GET /portal/catalogue/expblueprint<?[filter_parameters]>			
URI Query Parameters	Site	String	5G EVE site where the experiment can be deployed

	VsbId	String	ID of the VSB which the queried experiments blueprints are associated to.
Response body	expBlueprintInfo	List<ExpBlueprintInfo>	List of the experiment blueprints information elements matching the filter provided in the URI Query parameters.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 45: REST API - POST /portal/catalogue/expblueprint

POST /portal/catalogue/expblueprint			
Request body	experimentBlueprint	ExperimentBlueprint	Content of the experiment blueprint to be onboarded.
	nsds	List<Nsd>	NSD of the Network Services required to deploy the experiment elements.
	translationRules	List<TranslationRule>	Rules regulating the translation between an experiment descriptor based on the given blueprint and the associated network service.
	enhancedVsbs	Map<String, Nsd>	Map containing the VSB atomic component ID as the key, and the NSD containing the context components together with the vertical service components as the value. Used for multi-site experiments
	contextComponent	Map<String, String>	Map containing the context blueprint id as the key and the correspondent VSB atomic component id. Used for multi-site experiments
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 46: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/expblueprint/<id>

GET /portal/catalogue/expblueprint/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the queried experiment blueprint.
Response body	blueprintId	String	Unique ID of the experiment blueprint.
	version	String	Version of the experiment blueprint.
	name	String	Name of the experiment blueprint.
	experimentBlueprint	ExperimentBlueprint	Content of the experiment blueprint.
	activeExpdId	List<String>	IDs of the experiment descriptors associated to the given blueprint.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			

Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR

Table 47: REST API - DELETE /portal/catalogue/expblueprint/<id>

DELETE /portal/catalogue/expblueprint/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the experiment blueprint to be deleted.
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 48: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor<?[filter_parameters]>

GET /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor			
URI Query Parameters	--	--	--
Response body	expdID	List<String>	List of IDs of the available experiment descriptors.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 49: REST API - POST /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor

POST /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor			
Request body	name	String	Name of the experiment descriptor
	version	String	Version of the experiment descriptor
	experimentBlueprintId	String	ID of the associated experiment blueprint
	tenantId	String	ID of the tenant who is creating the experiment descriptor
	isPublic	Boolean	True if the experiment descriptor is public
	vsDescriptor	VsDescriptor	Descriptor of the associated vertical service
	contextDetails	List<BlueprintUserInformation>	Information provided by the experimenter about the configuration of the contexts associated to the experiment
	testCaseConfiguration	List<BlueprintUserInformation>	Information provided by the experimenter about the configuration of the test cases associated to the experiment
	kpiThresholds	Map<String,String>	Thresholds to evaluate the KPIs.
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a
Successful response HTTP code: 201 CREATED			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 409 CONFLICT, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 50: REST API - GET /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor/<id>

GET /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the queried experiment blueprint.
Response body	expDescriptor	ExperimentDescriptor	Content of the experiment descriptor.
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

Table 51: REST API - DELETE /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor/<id>

DELETE /portal/catalogue/expdescriptor/<id>			
URI Query Parameters	id	String	Unique ID of the experiment descriptor to be deleted.
Response body	n/a	n/a	n/a
Successful response HTTP code: 204 NO CONTENT			
Error response HTTP code: 400 BAD REQUEST, 403 FORBIDDEN, 404 NOT FOUND, 500 INTERNAL ERROR			

2.1.5.2 Implementation updates

Implementation details can be found in 5G EVE deliverables D4.1 [2] and D4.2 [3]. As stated before, this release of the Catalogue Service includes support for two new functionalities.

- Support for multi-site experiments, for managing the instantiation of experiments across multiple 5G EVE sites;
- Support for RAN slice parameters, for defining the specific RAN requirements of the services associated to the experiments.

Figure 4: Catalogue Service High-level architecture

Figure 4 shows the Catalogue service architecture established in D4.1 [2], highlighting in green the components which were updated in this final release:

- **Translator service interface**, this interface used internally for the translation of the experiment requests into a combination of NSDs, deployment flavours and instantiation levels, was updated to enable the translation of the nested components of the end-to-end service;
- **Experiment blueprint catalogue interface**, the interface was updated to add two parameters: *enhancedVsbs* and *contextComponent*. The first one is used to provide the NSDs of the vertical services enhanced with experiment context components, while the second one maps the context to the Atomic component of the VSB;
- **VSB/VSD catalogue service**, the internal logic of the services was updated to enable the management of multi-site VSB and the associated VSDs;
- **Information Model**, the information models were updated as described in section 2.3.
- **SOL 001/005 driver**, the driver was updated to include the composite NSD translation logic, in order to be able to onboard composite NSDs in the IWL Catalogue.

2.1.6 Ticketing System Backend

The Ticketing System Backend (TSB) component provides a REST API service to other modules at the backend as well as to the Ticketing GUI module through the *Itsb* interface. This interface is used to create, comment and delete tickets. The main functionality of this module is to notify events like errors, experiment requests, VNF onboarding requests, etc. to the corresponding actors who have to manage such events. The design of this module has been already presented in D4.1 [2], Section 4.2.

2.1.6.1 Ticketing System Backend Interface (Itsb)

Next, we introduce all endpoints defined by the ticketing system backend component. Table 52 shows a summary of all these endpoints, presenting the type of method, the URI suffix, a short description and if the endpoint is public or not. After that, tables from Table 53 until Table 62 present all those endpoints in detail, so any developer can construct a request, including the required parameters, their type, and a short description of every parameter. Furthermore, those tables include the parameters included in a successful response, and the type of codes expected, both for errors and correct messages.

Table 52: Ticketing System backend REST API

HTTP method.	URI	Description	Public
GET	/portal/tsb/products	Find available products that are susceptible for ticket association	Yes
GET	/portal/tsb/components	Find available components that are susceptible for ticket association	Yes
GET	/portal/tsb/adminusers	Find admin users to whom tickets can be assigned	Yes
POST	/portal/tsb/tickets	Add a new ticket	Yes
GET	/portal/tsb/tickets	Find tickets susceptible to be checked by the user	Yes
POST	/portal/tsb/tickets/trusted	Add a new ticket from a trusted module without authorization mechanisms	No
GET	/portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}	Retrieve specific information of a ticket	Yes
GET	/portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments	Retrieve comments associated to a ticket	Yes
POST	/portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments	Create a new comment at a specific ticket	Yes

POST	/portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments/trusted	Create a new comment at a specific ticket from a trusted module without authorization mechanisms	No
-------------	--	--	----

Table 53: REST API - GET /portal/tsb/products

GET /portal/tsb/products			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body (JSON)	Details	Array<String>	List of available product names
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			

Table 54: REST API - GET /portal/tsb/components

GET /portal/tsb/components			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body (JSON)	details	Array<String>	List of available components
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED			

Table 55: REST API - GET /portal/tsb/adminusers

GET /portal/tsb/adminusers			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body	--	--	--
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body (JSON)	Details	Array<String>	List of admin users susceptible of tickets association
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED			

Table 56: REST API - POST /portal/tsb/tickets

POST /portal/tsb/tickets			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	product	String	Product name at which the ticket will be created
	component	String	Component name at which the ticket will be created
	summary	String	Summary of the ticket to be created
	description	String	Description of the ticket
	assigned_to (optional)	email	Email address of the user in charge of managing the ticket
URI Variables	--	--	--

Response body	Details	String	ID of the newly created ticket
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 57: REST API - GET /portal/tsb/tickets

GET /portal/tsb/tickets			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	--	--	--
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body (JSON)	Details	Array<tickets>	List of tickets
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED			

Table 58: REST API - GET /portal/tsb/tickets/trusted

POST /portal/tsb/tickets/trusted			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	product	String	Product name at which the ticket will be created
	component	String	Component name at which the ticket will be created
	summary	String	Summary of the ticket to be created
	description	String	Description of the ticket
	assigned_to (optional)	email	Email address of the user in charge of managing the ticket
URI Variables	--	--	--
Response body	Details	String	ID of the newly created ticket
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 59: REST API - GET /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}

GET /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	--	--	--
URI Variables	ticket_id	String	Id of the ticket to be retrieved
Response body (JSON)	Details	ticket	Requested ticket
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED			

Table 60: REST API - GET /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments

GET /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description

Request body (JSON)	--	--	--
URI Variables	ticket_id	String	Id of the ticket whose comments we want to retrieve
Response body (JSON)	Details	Array<comments>	List of comments associated to the specific ticket
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED			

Table 61: REST API - POST /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments

POST /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	comment	String	Comment to be created at the ticket
URI Variables	ticket_id	String	Id of the ticket whose comments we want to retrieve
Response body (JSON)	Details	String	Id of the newly created comment
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

Table 62: REST API - POST /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments/trusted

POST /portal/tsb/tickets/{ticket_id}/comments/trusted			
	Parameter name	Parameter type	Description
Request body (JSON)	comment	String	Comment to be created at the ticket
URI Variables	ticket_id	String	Id of the ticket whose comments we want to retrieve
Response body (JSON)	Details	String	Id of the newly created comment
Successful response HTTP code: 200 OK			
Error response HTTP code: 401 UNAUTHORIZED, 400 BAD REQUEST			

2.1.6.2 Implementation updates

This component was not updated since the last version of the 5G EVE Portal, and the last implementation details can be found in D4.4 [1].

2.2 Portal GUI

The GUI was extended since the previous version of the Portal documented in D4.4 [1] to include new fields required by the changes done to the 5G EVE information model, in order to implement the multi-site experiments functionality. Thus, in this section we only include the main modifications to the components that have changed since the last version so, to have a full reference of all these improvements, please check D4.4 [1].

2.2.1 Data Visualization

Although the DCS-DV architecture has been already presented before, for the sake of clarity it is presented again in Figure 5, highlighting the components belonging to this module in the 5G EVE Portal.

Figure 5: Final DV architecture

In particular, Kibana is the main component of the DV. For the final version of the DCS-DV, Nginx has been also included to act as a proxy for managing the authentication of users with the RBAC, using the port 25601 (used by the Portal GUI when accessing to the dashboards) for that purpose. However, for creating the dashboards from the Dashboards' Handler in the DCS, the standard Kibana port (5601) is used.

Regarding the rest of functionalities of the DV, as they have not been changed from D4.4 [1], please refer to that deliverable to find all the details about that.

Finally, in the same way as with the DCS, the deployment of the DV, together with the DCS, has been done with a specific Ansible playbook that configures an Ubuntu Server 16.04 LTS from scratch, provisioning all the packages, files and tools needed to integrate the Monitoring platform in 5G EVE. This Ansible playbook can be found here: <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-dv-deployment> (v0.2 tag).

2.3 5G EVE Information Model

The implementation of the multi-site functionality imposed some changes to the information model defined in previous deliverables [2], [4], so this section is devoted to present the main modifications of the 5G EVE information model, compared to the previous version. Note that we include all Blueprints defined in the 5G EVE project for the sake of completeness, but we have highlighted in bold the changes compared with the previous versions.

2.3.1 Vertical Service Blueprint

Table 63 reports the fields composing a VSB with their short description. In bold we highlight the fields added or modified for this release. Further details about this descriptor can be found in D4.3 [4].

Table 63: VSB Information Model

Field	Description
blueprintId	Unique Identifier for the VSB.
version	A version number.
name	Name for the VSB.
description	Short description of the VSB.
parameters	List of parameters. The list provides for each parameter its name, type, description, and the field of applicability.
atomicComponents	List of atomic functional components (i.e., network functions, virtual applications and nested Vertical Services) needed to implement the VSB. Multi-site VSBs contain atomic components which reference the nested VSB ID and the target 5G EVE site.
interSite	Boolean value indicating if the VSB is multi-site or not.
endPoints	Specification of connection endpoints. They can be internal or external. Contains the slice type (i.e. eMBB, URLLC, etc) of this endpoint.
connectivityServices	List of virtual links and their relevant end points. Virtual links describe how the atomic functional components are connected.
serviceSequence	Description of how traffic flows among VNFs, supporting also multicast scenarios.
configurableParameters	Parameters that can be configured by the user for a specific instance of service derived from the given blueprint.
applicationMetrics	List of metrics that this service can provide. Metrics reported here are strictly application related. No network metrics are included.
compatibleSites	List of 5G EVE sites where the vertical service can be deployed.
compatibleContextBlueprint	List of IDs of the blueprints defining the experiment execution contexts that are compatible with the given vertical service.

2.3.2 Context Blueprint

Table 64 presents the fields defined for the Context Blueprint, and a short description associated to each field.

Table 64. Context Blueprint Information Model

Field	Description
blueprintId	Unique Identifier for the CtxB.
Version	A version number.
Name	Name for the CtxB.
description	Short description of the CtxB.
parameters	List of parameters. The list provides for each parameter its name, type, description, and the field of applicability.
atomicComponents	List of atomic functional components (i.e., network functions and virtual applications in general) needed to implement the CtxB.
endPoints	Specification of connection endpoints. They can be internal or external.
connectivityServices	List of virtual links and their relevant end points. Virtual links describe how the atomic functional components are connected.
configurableParameters	Parameters that can be configured by the user for a specific instance of execution context derived from the given blueprint.
applicationMetrics	List of metrics that this execution context can provide. Metrics reported here are strictly application related. No network metrics are included.
compatibleSites	List of 5G EVE sites where the vertical service can be deployed.
compositionStrategy	The strategy to be used by the Experiment Blueprint Builder (EBB) to compose this CtxB with a VSB. One of PASS THROUGH or CONNECT.

More details can be found in 5G EVE deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.3 [4].

2.3.3 Experiment Blueprint

Table 65 summarizes all fields that constitute an Experiment Blueprint, with a short description to explain each of them.

Table 65. Experiment Blueprint Information Model

Field	Description
expBlueprintId	Unique Identifier for the ExpB.
version	A version number.
name	Name for the ExpB.
description	Short description of the ExpB.
vsBlueprintId	The identifier of the VSB this experiment was built from.
ctxBlueprintIds	List of the identifiers of the CtxBs this experiment was built from.
tcBlueprintIds	List of the identifiers of the TcBs this experiment includes. Test cases are parameter-based templates that describe the concrete actions to be executed during the experiment.
sites	The trial sites involved in this experiment. This determines the radio coverage for this experiment.
infrastructureMetrics	List of infrastructure metrics to be monitored for this experiment.

kpis	List of KPIs to be validated for this experiment. They can be both application and network KPIs.
------	--

More details can be found in 5G EVE deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.3 [4].

2.3.4 Test Case Blueprint

In Table 66 we show all fields declared in a Test Case Blueprint, and a short description for each one.

Table 66. Test Case Blueprint Information Model

Field	Description
testcaseBlueprintId	Unique Identifier for the Test Case Blueprint
Script	Source code of the script to be executed
userParameters	Mapping of script variables to user parameters for the test customization
infrastructureParameters	Mapping of script variables to infrastructure parameters for the dynamic test configuration based on the specific NS related to the experiment (e.g., IP addresses)

More details can be found in 5G EVE deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.3 [4].

2.3.5 Metrics

Table 67 reports the fields composing the Metrics with their short description. In bold, the parameters added in this release are highlighted. Further details about this descriptor can be found in D4.1 [2] and D4.3 [4].

Table 67: Metric Information Model

Field	Description
metricId	Unique Identifier for the metric.
name	Name for the CB.
metricCollectionType	Can be one of the following: CUMULATIVE, DELTA, GAUGE.
unit	The measurement unit of the metric (e.g., seconds).
interval	The sampling interval of this metric.
topic (application metric only)	Topic for publish/subscribe broker. Needed for collecting data.
iMetricType (infrastructure metric only)	The infrastructure metric type.
targetSite (infrastructure metric only)	Used for multi-site experiments to determine the site producing the infrastructure metric.

2.3.6 KPI

This information model has not been updated, so all the details can be found in 5G EVE deliverables D4.1 [2] and D4.3 [4].

2.3.7 Experiment Descriptor

The Vertical Service Descriptor, which is referenced inside the Experiment Descriptor has been updated as detailed in Table 68. In bold, the parameters added in this release are highlighted.

Table 68: VSD Information Model

Field	Description
vsDescriptorId	Unique Identifier for the VSD.
version	A version number.
name	Name for the VSD.
description	Short description of the VSD.
managementType	An enumerator: PROVIDER_MANAGED/TENANT_MANAGED.
qosParameters	Map containing the values for the QoS input parameters of the associated VSB.
sliceProfiles	Map containing the RAN slice profiles associated with the different VSB end-points.
nestedVsdIds	List of the IDs of the nested VSD created for a multi-site VSB.

2.3.8 VNFD, PNFD and NSD

This information model has not been updated, so all the details can be found in 5G EVE deliverables D4.1 [2] and D4.3 [4].

3 5G EVE Portal workflow

The workflow to design, define, onboard, execute and validate an experiment is similar to the one already presented in previous deliverables, like in D4.4 [1]. The main difference is the preparation of the composite blueprints and descriptors to define multi-site experiments and the access in real-time to the monitoring platform. We have extended the 5G EVE Portal user manual with the one available in D4.4 [1] and the full documentation is available in the annex of this document, but in Table 69 we have included the main changes to the last user manual defined in D4.4 [1].

Table 69: Main changes to the user manual with respect to deliverable D4.4 [1]

Phase	Main changes	Reference
Design of blueprints and NSDs	Design of multi-site composite VSB	A.3.2.1
	Design of multi-site composite NSD	A.3.2.2
Experiment Design	Multi-site composite descriptors design	A.4.4
Monitoring & KPI reporting tools	DCS Component API	A.10.1

4 Conclusions

This document presents the final version of the 5G EVE experimental Portal. With the publication of this deliverable, and the access through the public portal to all services offered by the project, the 5G EVE project, and particularly its work package 4, has fully addressed objectives 5 and 8, as defined in the proposal. These objectives are:

- Objective 5: Develop a vertical-oriented open framework, consisting of intent-based mechanisms, APIs, and tools, facilitating the specification and deployment of multiple, end-to-end, multi-site and concurrent trials;
- Objective 8: To enhance the openness of the 5G-EVE end to end facility by allowing modular replacement of components and the coexistence of proprietary and Open Source technologies.

With respect to objective 8, all tools used in this work package are open source and, furthermore, all results are also open source, and can be found in <https://github.com/5GEVE>. With respect to objective 5, the 5G EVE Portal, together with other tools developed in the 5G EVE project allowed the design, definition, onboarding, instantiation, execution and validation of several experiments in different use cases. We would like to highlight the gaming use case, which is one of the multi-site use case defined by partners involved in the 5G EVE project. This challenging use case is successfully deployed over the 5G EVE infrastructure, executed between two different sites, and controlled via the 5G EVE management infrastructure deployed in two different sites. Thus, we can conclude that we have successfully addressed all the objectives initially declared within the project.

Finally, it is important to highlight that, apart from achieving all objectives defined in the 5G EVE proposal, we have extended the functionality of the Portal by following the feedback provided by other projects using our infrastructure, and in particular by some ICT-19 projects. For example, we have extended the Portal REST API to allow clients to collect live or stored metrics generated by their experiments.

Acknowledgment

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ANNEX

A.5G EVE PORTAL USER GUIDE

A.1. REGISTRATION ON THE PLATFORM

- To register on the platform, go to the login page of the portal at <https://portal.5g-eve.eu/#/login>. Once there click on the “Register” button as indicated in Figure 6:

Figure 6: Login page

- On clicking the “Register” button, you will be provided with a page similar to the one shown in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Registration page

- Fill in your registration details and click on submit; all fields are compulsory.
- On clicking submit, your registration request will be sent to the 5G EVE administrators in charge of authentication on the platform. Therefore, this registration is not automatic, i.e. you will not be given instant access upon registration. Rather after your role on the 5G EVE platform has been confirmed accordingly.
- Once your registration has been successful, you will receive a notification email. Henceforth, you can proceed to use the 5G EVE platform to design, run and execute your experiments.

A.2. ONBOARDING OF VNF PACKAGES

- The main objective of VNF provider actors is to upload the VNF packages associated to the Vertical Service that other actors will use to run on the platform.
- To this end, the 5G EVE platform provides the “VNF Onboard tool”. This tool can be used to onboard VNF packages (i.e. images, VNF descriptors, and metadata, etc.) to the 5G EVE platform.
- So, depending on the requirements of the Management and Network Orchestration (MANO) platform of the specific 5G EVE site(s) where experiment and experiment developers want to deploy their experiments, these VNF packages can be uploaded using this tool.
- To be able to onboard your VNF package to the platform, you need to prepare the following files/folders:
 - i) VNF Image: this is the actual base image of your VNF, saved in the preferable format for the considered MANO platform;
 - ii) VNF descriptor: this should be a zipped folder containing your VNF descriptor package;
 - iii) Any additional requisite files depending on the MANO platform under consideration.
- Once these files have been prepared, zip the files into a single folder (the acceptable zip format is “.zip”); subsequently, we can proceed to upload the zipped VNF folder to the platform using the VNF Onboard tool.
- To use the tool, go to the portal and login with the email address and password you provided during the registration procedure. Upon logging in, you will be provided with the portal home page shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: 5G EVE portal home page

- Go ahead and click on the “Design Experiments” tab. Once inside, select the “Virtual Network Functions list” tab as illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: VNF Onboarding tool

- By clicking on the “Virtual Network Functions list” tab, you will be redirected to a page similar to the one given in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Select VNF Onboard tool

- Go ahead and click on the “Onboard VNFs” tab and you will see a page similar to the one in Figure 11.

Figure 11: VNF Onboarding tool

- This tool provides four main functionalities:

- i) VNF Uploading and creation of deployment requests (represented by the “Upload VNF” tab in Figure 11): used to upload the VNF packages;
 - ii) Created VNF Deployment requests list (represented by the “Deployment Requests” tab in Figure 11): used to upload the VNF package to the MANO platform of the specified 5G EVE site;
 - iii) Uploaded VNFs List (represented by the “My VNFs” tab in Figure 11): used to display a list of your uploaded VNFs and supports a re-deployment of the same VNF to different 5G EVE sites;
 - iv) Update VNF list (represented by the “Update List” button in Figure 11): this button is used to force the update of the VNF deployment requests list in case the VNF list is not automatically updated.
- These four functionalities are discussed further in the following sections.

A.2.1. VNF Uploading and creation of deployment requests

- To upload your VNF package, click on the “Upload VNF” tab in Figure 12. On clicking on this tab, you will be redirected to a page similar to Figure 12.

Figure 12: Upload VNF and Create Deployment Request

- In order to onboard your VNF package on the platform, follow the steps below:
 - i) Input the preferred name of your VNF file (indicated as step 1 in Figure 12);
 - ii) Next, click on the “select file” icon to upload your zipped VNF package folder i.e., containing all your VNF details (indicated as step 2 in Figure 12);
 - iii) Thirdly, select the 5G EVE site name where you want your VNF to be uploaded (indicated as step 3 in Figure 12);
 - iv) Finally, click on the “Upload File” button to upload your VNF package folder (indicated as step 4 in Figure 12).
- An example of a complete VNF Upload and deployment request is provided in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Complete VNF deployment request

A.2.2. Created VNF Deployment Requests List

- Once your VNF package has been successfully uploaded and the deployment request created, you can proceed to view the status of your deployment request using the “Deployment Requests” tab.
- For example, in Figure 14, we can view the recently uploaded VNF package in section A.2.1 called “simple_vnf.zip,” the 5G EVE site where the request was sent (in this case the “SPAIN_5TONIC” site), and its current status is “PENDING”; which means waiting for approval and deployment by the site manager of the “SPAIN_5TONIC” site.

Request ID	Filename	Associated Site	Status	Actions
d228991-e1ef-41e7-ba80-e8d81a3c48b5	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	FRANCE_RENNES	READY	🔍 🗑️
79f07da2-b6c3-4d44-ad61-c548e1036c3	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	GREECE_ATHENS	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
86a2a06-3a88-4083-a072-d843870421e	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d7957f83-5462-4b3d-b6d9-e4c8b08836	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	ITALY_TURIN	READY	🔍 🗑️
34c8712a-48a7-43a5-9729-474a78a7897	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
0b23172f-2283-4f69-9375-357aa746009	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
ee84596-b06c-4a3c-8a71-89a587041ea	VNF_test_upload_4.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d780972-38d1-48c1-9d25-45efab268db	VNF_test_upload_5.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
2c0a8a8-052c-4879-a110-555aa0546d8	VNF_test_upload_10.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
a4236e67-ef40-4a2b-846c-5a367831c1d	simple_vnf.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️

Figure 14: Created Deployment Requests

- Once this deployment request is accepted by the site manager and your VNF package has been uploaded, the deployment status will change to “READY” as indicated in Figure 15. At this point, your VNF deployment request has been accepted, and will be available on the platform in due time.

Request ID	Filename	Associated Site	Status	Actions
d228991-e1ef-41e7-ba80-e8d81a3c48b5	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	FRANCE_RENNES	READY	🔍 🗑️
79f07da2-b6c3-4d44-ad61-c548e1036c3	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	GREECE_ATHENS	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
86a2a06-3a88-4083-a072-d843870421e	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d7957f83-5462-4b3d-b6d9-e4c8b08836	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	ITALY_TURIN	READY	🔍 🗑️
34c8712a-48a7-43a5-9729-474a78a7897	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
0b23172f-2283-4f69-9375-357aa746009	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
ee84596-b06c-4a3c-8a71-89a587041ea	VNF_test_upload_4.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
d780972-38d1-48c1-9d25-45efab268db	VNF_test_upload_5.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
2c0a8a8-052c-4879-a110-555aa0546d8	VNF_test_upload_10.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	PENDING	🔍 🗑️
a4236e67-ef40-4a2b-846c-5a367831c1d	simple_vnf.zip	SPAIN_5TONIC	READY	🔍 🗑️

Figure 15: Accepted VNF Deployment Request

A.2.3. Uploaded VNFs List

- To view your Uploaded VNFs, click on the “My VNFs” tab as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Uploaded VNFs List

- As you can see from Figure 16, we can see our newly uploaded VNF i.e., simple_vnf.zip (indicated as step (1)) and also have the option of downloading it (indicated as step (2)).
- Next, if we wanted to upload this VNF to a second 5G EVE site for example, the “ITALY_TURIN” site, we click on the “arrow” button (indicated as step (3) in Figure 16) corresponding to the VNF we wish to re-deploy.
- On clicking on the “arrow” button, we are presented with a page similar to Figure 17 and we select the new 5G EVE site where we wish to re-deploy this VNF, in this particular case, we chose the “ITALY_TURIN” site, henceforth, we click on the “Create” button to submit the deployment request.

Figure 17: Re-deploy VNF request

- On creating the deployment request, we can view this request under the “Deployment Requests” tab as indicated Figure 18.

Request ID	Filename	Associated Site	Status	Actions
d72385f1-e1ef-417-6a05-e48113c0f55	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	FRANCE_RENNES	READY	[Icons]
79f016a2-ba03-4044-a9a1-ca04b41030c3	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	GREECE_ATHENS	PENDING	[Icons]
846a3a56-3a84-4083-a072-08438795421e	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	[Icons]
d795f768-58d2-4886-ba95-a433a0b0883a	VNF_test_upload_3.zip	ITALY_TURIN	READY	[Icons]
0a473603-7a11-4a6b-ac23-a65598753463	simple_vnf.zip	ITALY_TURIN	PENDING	[Icons]
34a8712d-48e7-43e5-9729-476a778a7887	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	[Icons]
0a231720-3283-41a9-9375-357aa7466a09	VNF_test_upload_2.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	[Icons]
ee84d594-4b7e-4a3c-8a71-89e0577611a1	VNF_test_upload_4.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	[Icons]
d7807972-38a1-48c1-9c25-45ef4623a08b	VNF_test_upload_6.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	[Icons]
21caba89-962c-4079-ad10-5b5aa03c4d68	VNF_test_upload_10.zip	SPAIN_STONC	PENDING	[Icons]
a4223a67-fef0-4629-8a0c-9a3678031c1d	simple_vnf.zip	SPAIN_STONC	READY	[Icons]

Figure 18: Re-deploy VNF request status

A.2.4. Update VNF List

- Finally, the “Update List” button in Figure 19 can be used to force the update of the VNF list.

Filename	Owner	Last Updated	Actions
VNF_test_upload_1.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15,Oct,2020	[Icons]
VNF_test_upload_2.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15,Oct,2020	[Icons]
VNF_test_upload_3.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15,Oct,2020	[Icons]
VNF_test_upload_4.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	19,Oct,2020	[Icons]
VNF_test_upload_5.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	20,Oct,2020	[Icons]
VNF_test_upload_10.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	28,Oct,2020	[Icons]
simple_vnf.zip	esp_dev@mail.com	15,Dec,2020	[Icons]

Figure 19: Update VNF List

A.3. DESIGN OF BLUEPRINTS AND NETWORK SERVICE DESCRIPTORS (NSDs)

- To design an experiment on the platform, initially, experiment developers have to prepare three types of blueprints, i.e., Vertical Service Blueprints (VSB), Context Blueprints (CtxBs), and Test Case Blueprints (TCB) (see 5G-EVE D4.3 [4] for more information). If you are an experiment developer, the number of context blueprints depends on the number of contexts you want to consider in your experiment. For example, in the simplest use-case, we are considering one type of context, i.e., delay, and as a result, we have only one CtxB.
- For these blueprints (i.e., VSB, CtxBs and TCBs), the corresponding blueprint fields and the meaning have been defined in (see 5G-EVE D4.3 [4] for more information).
- In summary, the VSB contains your vertical service components, virtual links and their interconnections.
- Whereas the CtxB contains the different network impairments, you want to apply to your vertical service. The 5G EVE platform provides two types of Context Blueprints, i.e., PASS_THROUGH and CONNECT (see 5G-EVE D4.3 [4] for more information). Before designing your CtxB, please ensure that you are familiar with each type of CtxB since this will affect how the composed NSD will be generated.
- And finally, the TCB contains the different actions/tests that are to be carried out on the vertical service. A detailed description of the TCB parameters is provided in section A.4.2.2.
- The 5G EVE platform provides a fourth type of blueprint called the Experiment Blueprint (ExpB); however, for this blueprint, the platform provides a wizard, so you don't need to design it beforehand. More details about this blueprint can be found in section A.4.3.
- The VSB, CtxB and ExpB should all have a corresponding NSD.
- The 5G EVE platform only accepts descriptors (i.e., blueprints and NSDs) in the “JSON” format.
- To assist in the design of Blueprints and the generation of NSDs, the 5G EVE portal provides the “Blueprint and NSD support tool”; in the subsequent sections, this tool will be discussed further.

A.3.1. Blueprint and NSD Support tool

- This tool can assist in the design of blueprints and the generation of the corresponding NSDs. To be able to use this tool to generate your NSDs reliably, please ensure to have the following in mind when designing your blueprints:
 - i) When preparing the blueprints, the atomic components' component id should correspond to the UUID of the VNF inside your VNFD descriptor file. This value of the component id will be translated into the VNFD id inside the NSD;
 - ii) Ensure that the endpoints defined in the blueprints correspond to the connection points defined in the VNFD file. The blueprint's endpoint names will be translated into the VNFD service access and connection points depending on the nomenclature used with the blueprints' endpoints. The connection points containing "sap" anywhere within the name will be translated into service access points (saps); it doesn't matter if it's lower-case or uppercase;
 - iii) Ensure to attach a service access point to every virtual link where you need a mapping to an existing network in your data centre. Depending on whether the service access point has been defined as a management sap or not, this will determine which existing network your VNF will be attached to during the network service instantiation;
 - iv) Moreover, when defining your endpoints, be careful about the "ranConnection: true/false" property because this will determine how your VNFs will be connected in the composed NSD. The endpoint with this property set to true should be a connection point that is reachable from the RAN and vice-versa. In particular, the algorithm will place the context(s) as close as possible to the RAN endpoint.

- Therefore, it is important that at least one "sap" endpoint has the "ranConnection: true" inside the VSB because the algorithm will match it with the SapDescriptor in the NSD;
- v) The VSB virtual link attached to this endpoint with "ranConnection: true" will be added to the CtxB and the other private virtual link in the CtxB will be used to connect the CtxB to the VSB component;
 - vi) Finally, when designing the CtxBs, care should be given to the value of the “compositionStrategy” parameter, since this will determine the type of CtxB you are using in your vertical service when composing the NSD.
- With those few pointers in mind, we can go ahead to use the tool to assist in the blueprints design and the generation of the corresponding NSDs.
 - To use the tool, go to the portal homepage page shown in Figure 8 and select the “Design Experiment” tab.
 - Upon clicking on this section, you will be presented with the page similar to Figure 20.

Figure 20: Design Experiments page

- To use the tool, click on the “Support Tools list” section as indicated in Figure 20.
- On clicking, you will be presented with a page similar to Figure 21.

Figure 21: Support tools page

- The tool provides four main functionalities:
 - i) Blueprint and NSD Schemas (indicated as “Schemas” in Figure 21);
 - ii) NSD generation (referred to as “Generate NSD” in Figure 21);
 - iii) NSD composition (referred to as “Composer” in Figure 21);
 - iv) Blueprint and NSD validation (indicated as “Validation” in Figure 21).

- In the following sections, we will discuss how to use each of the above functionalities to assist in the design your blueprints and generation of the network service descriptors on the platform.

A.3.1.1. Blueprint and NSD Schemas

- This tool contains the schemas for the different blueprints i.e., VSB, CtxB, TCB & ExpB and network service descriptors used on the platform.
- For each blueprint and NSD, you can download the corresponding schema and follow the specified format when designing your descriptors.
- For example, when designing the vertical service blueprint (VSB), you can download the equivalent schema as indicated in Figure 22.

Figure 22: VSB Schema download

- The same procedure can be followed for all the other blueprints and network service descriptors.
- An example of a VSB blueprint following this schema with an explanation of the different fields is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/VSB/vsb_simple.yaml
- The json equivalent of the VSB is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/VSB/vsb_simple.json
- The CtxB for this simple use case following the available CtxB schema is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/tree/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/CtxB/ctxb_simple.yaml
- The json equivalent of the CtxB is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/tree/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/CtxB/ctxb_simple.json
- The TCB for this simple use case following the available TCB schema is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/TCB/Simple_UC_TCB.yaml
- The json equivalent of the TCB is given in https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/TCB/Simple_UC_TCB.json

A.3.1.2. NSD Generation

- This tool can be used to generate NSDs corresponding to the blueprints designed in section A.3.1.1 above.
- To use this tool, go to the “Generate NSD” tab (step 1) and click on the “Choose file” button (step 2) to upload the blueprint (json format as it is presented in step 3) as indicated in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Generate NSD tool

- Finally, click on the “Download” button (step 4) to download the generated NSD and save it with a suitable filename. The generated NSD corresponding to the VSB presented in section A.3.1.1 above can be accessed at: https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/VSB/vsb_simple_nsd.json.
- The generated NSD corresponding to the CtxB presented in section A.3.1.1 above can be accessed at: https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/CtxB/ctxb_simple_nsd.json.

A.3.1.3. NSD Composition

- This tool referred to as “Composer” on the portal is used to combine the generated NSDs for the VSB and CtxBs from section A.3.1.2 to form a single “**Composite NSD**” that will be the actual NSD deployed by the platform.
- This “**Composite NSD**” is the NSD associated with the ExpB.
- To generate this “Composite NSD”, we follow the following steps:

Figure 24: NSD Composer tool

- First, upload the VSB (indicated as stage 1 in Figure 24);
- Next upload the corresponding NSD generated from section A.3.1.2 (indicated as stage 2 in Figure 24);
- Thirdly, upload the CtxB for your use case (indicated as stage 3 in Figure 24);

iv) Subsequently, upload the corresponding CtxB NSD (indicated as stage 4 in Figure 24).

Figure 25: Composed NSD download

v) Next, if you select the “Add Details” box (indicated as stage 5 in Figure 25), then the tool provides you with a graphical representation of the composed NSD. You can use this graph to confirm that the NSD composition is in line with what you were expecting and make the necessary changes if needed.

vi) Finally, by clicking on the “Download” button (indicated as stage 6 in Figure 25), you can download the composed NSD. This composed NSD is a zip folder with the composed NSD and a graphical representation of the composed NSD (“png format”). Save this composed NSD with a suitable file name.

- It is important to note that the “NSD Composition” tool will always place the experiment contexts as close as possible to the RAN. Therefore, if your experiment requires a more complex configuration, then in that case, by using the NSD schema provided in Section A.3.1.1, you can design your own Composite NSD.

A.3.1.4. Blueprint and NSD descriptors validation

- This tool can be used to validate all your blueprints and NSDs before uploading them to the portal.
- To verify any of the blueprints and NSDs, select the applicable schema depending on the blueprint or NSD you need to validate using the “arrow” button as illustrated in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Validate blueprints and NSDs

- For example, to validate that your VSB is correct, the first step is to select the “Vertical Service Blueprint Schema”, followed by uploading your VSB file. This process is illustrated in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Blueprints and NSD descriptors validation

- If your blueprint/NSD has no issues, then you will see the “validation SUCCESS” notification at the bottom of the page as indicated by step (3) in Figure 27. Otherwise, if your blueprint/NSD has any issues, then you will be given more details about the error sources.

A.3.2. Design of Multi-site Experiments’ Descriptors

- For the multi-site experiments, the experiment developers need to design the VSBs, CtxBs, and the corresponding NSDs for each of the sites included in the multi-site experiment. To design the blueprints and the NSDs, follow the steps mentioned in section A.3.1 above.
- Next, this is followed by the design of the inter-site VSB and the corresponding NSD. Accordingly, in the proceeding sections, we will discuss how to design the multi-site composite VSB and NSD.

A.3.2.1. Design of the Multi-site composite vertical service blueprint

- The multi-site VSB (sometimes referred to as the composite VSB) is the blueprint that encompasses all the VSBs for the constituent single sites involved in the multi-site experiment. Besides, this composite VSB can contain features related to the connectivity between the sites associated with the multi-site experiment.
- The features of this composite VSB are given in Table 70 below

Table 70: Multi-site composite VSB

Field	Type	Items_properties	Description
interSite	Boolean	N/A	Set to “true” for inter-site experiments

version	String	N/A	Composite VSB version number
name	String	N/A	Composite VSB name
description	String	N/A	Brief description of the multi-site experiment
parameters	Array	parameterId	Composite VSB parameter Id
		parameterName	Composite VSB parameter name
		parameterType	Composite VSB parameter type
		parameterDescription	Composite VSB parameter description
		applicabilityField	Field where this VSB parameter is used
atomicComponents	Array (Add an atomic component from each of the VSBs composing your composite VSB)	componentId	Atomic component Id for a constituent VSB (i.e., the single site VSB)
		serversNumber	The number of servers/VMs composing the atomic component
		compatibleSite	The compatible site for the constituent VSB
		Type	Type of atomic component, default is "SERVICE"
		associatedVsbId	The Id of the constituent VSB
applicationMetrics	Array	--	Composite VSB application metrics, data structure similar to the single-site VSB application metrics
endPoints	Array	--	Composite VSB endpoints, data structure similar to the single-site VSB endpoints
connectivityServices	Array	--	Composite VSB connectivity services, data structure similar to the single-site VSB connectivity services field.
compatibleSites	Array	--	A list of all the 5G EVE sites involved in this multi-site experiment. Valid values are: - ITALY_TURIN, SPAIN_5TONIC, FRANCE_PARIS, FRANCE_NICE, FRANCE_RENNES, GREECE_ATHENS

- An example of a simple composite VSB is given in Figure 28.

```

1  ---
2  interSite: true
3  version: '1.6'
4  name: Composite testing Service enhanced without radio_metrics
5  description: Composite VSB
6  parameters:
7  - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Spain
8    parameterName: Number of User Equipments
9    parameterType: number
10   parameterDescription: Number of web users_Spain
11   (Mandatory)
12   applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
13  - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Italy
14    parameterName: Number of User Equipments
15    parameterType: number
16    parameterDescription: Number of web users_Italy
17    (Mandatory)
18    applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
19  atomicComponents:
20  - componentId: " apache"
21    serversNumber: 1
22    compatibleSite: SPAIN_5TONIC
23    type: SERVICE
24    associatedVsbId: '211'
25  - componentId: tracker_turin
26    serversNumber: 1
27    associatedVsbId: '260'
28    compatibleSite: ITALY_TURIN
29    type: SERVICE
30  applicationMetrics: []
31  endPoints:
32  - endPointId: cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
33    external: true
34    management: false
35    ranConnection: true
36  connectivityServices:
37  - endPointIds:
38    - cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
39    management: true
40    external: true
41    name: tracker_ext
42  compatibleSites:
43  - SPAIN_5TONIC
44  - ITALY_TURIN

```

Figure 28: Simple Multi-site UC composite VSB

A.3.2.2. Design of the Multi-site composite NSD

- After designing the composite VSB for the multi-site experiment, we need to design the corresponding composite NSD.
- The features of the multi-site composite NSD are presented in Table 71.

Table 71: Multi-site Composite NSD

Field	Type	Item_properties	Item_properties_II	Description
nsdIdentifier	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD unique identifier
designer	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD designer
version	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD version

nsdName	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD name	
nsdInvariantId	String	N/A	N/A	Composite NSD Invariant Id	
nestedNsdId	Array	String	N/A	List of the nested NSD Ids comprising this composite NSD	
nsDf	Array	nsDfId	N/A	Specify the ID for the composite NS deployment flavor	
		flavourKey	N/A	Specify the key for the composite NS deployment flavor	
		This process is repeated for each possible NS instantiation level for the composite NSD			
		nsInstantiation-Level	nsLevelId		Specify the composite NS instantiation level Id.
			description		Add a description for the composite NS instantiation level.
			nsToLevelMapping: nsProfileId numberOf Instances		Specify the NS profile id for each of the nested NSDs. This NsProfileId should be the same as that specified inside the nested NSDs.
		defaultNsInstantiationLevelId	N/A		In case more than one NS instantiation level has been defined, specify the default instantiation level Id.
		For each of the nsProfileIds specified above, provide the following details			
		nsProfile	nsProfileId		Same as the one specified under the nsInstantiationLevel filed
			nsdId		The id of the nested NSD with the specified nsProfileId
			nsDfId		The nested NSD Deployment flavor Id
			nsInstantiationLevelId		The nested NSD Instantiation Level Id
minNumberOfInstances			The minimum number of the nested NSD instances to launch		
maxNumberOfInstances			The maximum number of the nested NSD instances to launch		

- An example of a multi-site composite NSD for the simple use case is provided in Figure 30

```
1 ---
2 nsdIdentifier: compositeNSD_metrics_v1
3 designer: NXW & UC3M
4 version: '1.0'
5 nsdName: compositeNSDName_metrics_v1
6 nsdInvariantId: compositeNSDInvariantId_v1
7 nestedNsdId:
8 - vsbNestedNSD_metrics
9 - vsbNestedNSD2_metrics
10 nsDf:
11 - nsDfId: compositeNSD_df
12   flavourKey: compositeNSD_df
13   nsInstantiationLevel:
14   - nsLevelId: compositeNSD_il_small
15     description: compositeNSD small instantiation level
16     nsToLevelMapping:
17     - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD_profile_small
18       numberOfInstances: 1
19     - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD2_profile_small
20       numberOfInstances: 1
21   defaultNsInstantiationLevelId: compositeNSD_il_small
22   nsProfile:
23   - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD_profile_small
24     nsdId: vsbNestedNSD_metrics
25     nsDfId: vsb_apache_simple_df
26     nsInstantiationLevelId: vsb_apache_simple_il_default
27     minNumberOfInstances: 1
28     maxNumberOfInstances: 1
29   - nsProfileId: vsbNestedNSD2_profile_small
30     nsdId: vsbNestedNSD2_metrics
31     nsDfId: nestedNSD_df
32     nsInstantiationLevelId: nestedNSD_il_small
33     minNumberOfInstances: 1
34     maxNumberOfInstances: 1
35   security:
36     signature: SIGNATURE
37     algorithm: ALGORITHM
38     certificate: CERTIFICATE
39
```

Figure 29: Simple multi-site UC composite NSD

A.4. EXPERIMENT DESIGN USING THE 5G EVE PORTAL

- After an experiment developer has designed the corresponding blueprints and generated the corresponding NSDs; experimenters can start designing their experiments.
- If you are an experimenter, to start designing your experiment, go to portal home page and select the “Design Experiments” tab as shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30: 5G EVE Portal Welcome Page

- Click on the Design Experiment icon, and you will be led to the design experiment page which looks similar to Figure 31.

Figure 31: 5G EVE Portal Experiment Design Page

- Once you are on the design experiment page, you will have access to all the different descriptors (i.e., blueprints, NSDs and VNFDs) available on the platform.
- And next, we shall proceed to upload our newly designed descriptors to the platform. So, go ahead and click on the “Blueprints” tab as indicated in Figure 31.

A.4.1. Uploading the Vertical Service Blueprint

- We are going to begin with the vertical service blueprints, and we will keep repeating the same steps for all the other blueprints.
- So, go ahead and click on the Vertical Service under the Blueprints section and you will be re-directed to a page similar to Figure 32.

Figure 32: 5G EVE Portal Vertical Service Blueprints Design Page

- As you can see, we have three tasks to perform here: Upload Blueprint, Upload NSDs and Create Translation Rules (indicated as step (2) in Figure 32).
- Beginning with task 1, upload the vertical service blueprint (VSB) from section A.3.
- Once you are done uploading the VSB, then click on the next button.
- Next, we move on to task 2 to upload the NSDs. As stated in section A.3 above, every VSB has a corresponding NSD, so go ahead and upload the NSD in json format (from section A.3) corresponding to your VSB. Once done, click the next button.
- Next, you will be directed to the create translation rules task; by this stage the portal would have already read the id and version of your uploaded NSD and they will be auto filled by the portal. Please refer to Figure 33 for more information.
- So, your only task is to select the Network Service (NS) Deployment Flavor id and Instantiation Level id that you want to use in this particular experiment.
- All the available NS Deployment Flavors and Instantiation Levels inside your NSD will be presented to you, and you just have to select using the “arrow” button the right combination of Deployment Flavor and Instantiation Level ids that you want to use.
- The next field is the parameters section, for this field the 5G EVE portal will have already read the “parameters” section of your VSB. Thereafter, the portal will present you with your VSB parameters, so that you can select the range of each VSB parameter that you want to use in your experiment.
- If your VSB has more than one parameter, then click on the “+” icon inside to add more parameters.

Figure 33: 5G EVE Portal VSB Translation Rules

- Once you are done filling in and selecting all the required parameters, then you can go ahead and click the “submit” button.

A.4.1.1. Verification of the VSB submission

- After clicking the “submit” button, if your submission was successful then you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed then you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, then please refer to section A.11 for some troubleshooting tips.
- Once the submission is successful, we can view our uploaded blueprint by clicking on the “view” tab as shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34: 5G EVE View Uploaded Blueprint

- As we can see in Figure 34, the submission was successful hence the ASTI AGV VSB is also listed.
- In order to view our uploaded blueprint, click on the eye icon as shown in Figure 34.
- Clicking on the eye icon, our blueprint looks as shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: 5G EVE Portal Uploaded VSB View

NOTE:

- Sometimes, it’s possible that your upload was successful however when you click on the eye icon, you are not able to view your blueprint.
- In that case, please refer to section A.11 for some trouble-shooting tips.
- Your VSB upload is only considered successful if you can view the VSB using the eye icon in the “view” tab.

A.4.2. Uploading of the Context Blueprints

- Go back to the blueprints section, and this time, select the Execution context as shown in Figure 36.
- The procedure to upload the execution context blueprints is the same as the procedure to upload the vertical service blueprints (section A.4.1), as shown in Figure 36.
- The only difference is that now you will be uploading the context blueprints from section A.3 with the corresponding NSDs instead of VSBs.

Figure 36: 5G EVE Execution Context Blueprints Upload

- Please remember that you have to upload all the context blueprints from section A.3 and the corresponding NSDs you expect to use in your experiment.
- Please refer to section A.4.1 above and apply the same principles to the context NSDs in your experiment to help understand the translation rules,
- Once done, please click the “submit” button.

A.4.2.1. Verification of the Execution Context Blueprints submission

- After clicking the “submit” button, if your submission was successful, then you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed, then you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, then please refer to section A.11 for some troubleshooting tips.
- To check that all the relevant context blueprints for your experiment have been successfully uploaded, please click on the “view” tab of your execution context blueprints. As we can see from the “view” tab, the two context blueprints were uploaded successfully for this use case, as shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37: 5G EVE Execution Context Blueprints view

- To verify that our context blueprints were successfully onboarded, we need to click on the “eye” icon for each of the context blueprints as shown in Figure 37.
- If the upload was successful, you will be able to view each of your uploaded context blueprints. In our case, the two contexts view looked, as shown in Figure 38 and Figure 39.

Figure 38: 5G EVE ASTI Use-case delay context blueprint view

Figure 39: 5G EVE ASTI Use-case Background traffic context blueprint view

- In case you can't view one or more of your context blueprints, please refer to section A.11 of this document for some troubleshooting tips.
- Once we are done uploading and verifying the uploaded context blueprints, we are ready to start on the test case blueprints.

A.4.2.2. Uploading of the Test Case Blueprints

- Go back to the blueprints section and this time, select “Test Case” blueprints, and you will be presented with a page similar to Figure 40.

Figure 40: 5G EVE Portal Test Case Blueprint Onboarding

- The platform provides two options for uploading the TCB i.e., Direct TCB Upload (indicated as step (2) in Figure 40) or Creating the TCB on the fly (indicated as step (3) in Figure 40).
- In the following sections, we are going to discuss the meaning of the different fields of the TCB and finally provide examples of TCBs based on the two options.

A.4.2.3. TCB parameters definition

- To begin with, let us try to understand what each of the test-case blueprint form parameters represent, based on the information shown in Figure 41:

Figure 41: TCB form

- The name, description and version parameters are compulsory. So, go ahead and fill them in.
- Just remember you can only have one combination of name and version for each test-case blueprint.
- So, let us focus on the highlighted parameters:
 - Label 1 - Configuration Script**
 - This parameter captures all the commands and/or scripts required to configure your vertical service to be ready to produce the application and/or infrastructure metrics.
 - Label 2 - Execution Script**
 - This parameter captures all the commands and/or scripts required to generate the application and/or infrastructure metrics for your vertical service test case.
 - Label 3 - Reset configuration Script**
 - This optional parameter captures all the commands and/or scripts required to clean/clear your vertical service environment after it has finished executing the test case.
 - Label 4 - User Parameters**
 - Here, we provide all the parameters needed to access our vertical service components (e.g., authentication) and run the test case (e.g., script arguments).
 - This can also include the user parameters required to access and run the context components.
 - Use the “+” icon to add more user parameters.
 - Label 5 - Infrastructure Parameters**
 - These are the parameters that should be provided by the 5G EVE platform to your test case for successful execution.
 - Examples include: VNF ip addresses, application metric topic id to publish the data too, so that it’s viewable in the 5G EVE monitoring and reporting tool.

- Once you are done filling in the test case blueprint (TCB) parameters, then you can submit your TCB by clicking on the “submit” button.

A.4.2.4. TCB Examples

- An example of a filled-in test case blueprint is given in Figure 42.

Figure 42: 5G EVE Portal Simple_UseCase_TCB

- On the other hand, an example of a simple TCB that can be uploaded directly to the platform is available at https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-yaml/blob/master/UC_0.1_ApacheSimple/Support_tools/TCB/Simple_UC_TCB.json

A.4.2.5. Verification of the Test Case Blueprints submission

- After clicking on the “submit” button, if your submission was successful, you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed, you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, please refer to section A.11 for some troubleshooting tips.
- To verify that your submission was successful, click of the “view” tab of the test case blueprints, and you will see your submitted TCB in the list. For our example, this is illustrated in Figure 43.

ID	Name	Version	Description	User Parameters	Infrastructure Parameters
12	Apache Simple TCB	1.0	Apache Simple TCB	parameters: ExperimentName: Apache Simple TCB, version: 1.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
41	TCB BESS/TUP test case 1	1.0	Test case to run the BESS/TUP use case	parameters: ExperimentName: TCB BESS/TUP test case 1, version: 1.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
54	Apache_TCB_v2	2.0	TCB Apache simple v2	parameters: ExperimentName: Apache_TCB_v2, version: 2.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
71	Apache_TCB_v3	3.0	Apache_TCB_v3	parameters: ExperimentName: Apache_TCB_v3, version: 3.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
80	test_sash	1.0	test_sash	parameters: ExperimentName: test_sash, version: 1.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
100	TCB BESS/TUP test case 2	1.0	Test case to run the BESS/TUP use case 2	parameters: ExperimentName: TCB BESS/TUP test case 2, version: 1.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
118	Apache_TCB_v4_06	2.0	Apache_TCB_v4_06	parameters: ExperimentName: Apache_TCB_v4_06, version: 2.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
128	apache_sash_v4_06_v2	2.0	apache_sash_v4_06_v2	parameters: ExperimentName: apache_sash_v4_06_v2, version: 2.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
144	TCB BESS/TUP test case 31	3.1	Test case to run the BESS/TUP use case 31	parameters: ExperimentName: TCB BESS/TUP test case 31, version: 3.1, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/
162	apache_sash	1.0	TCB for the Simple Apache Use Case	parameters: ExperimentName: apache_sash, version: 1.0, user: superuser	infrastructure: request: time: 1min, uri: http://10.0.0.1:8080/

Figure 43: 5G EVE Simple_Usecase_TCB View

- Once we are done verifying the test case blueprints, then we are ready to move on to the Experiment blueprints.

A.4.3. Uploading of the Experiment Blueprints

- In order to design the Experiment Blueprint, go back to the “descriptors” section and select Experiment as shown in Figure 44.

Figure 44: 5G EVE Portal Experiment Blueprint Design

- The fields highlighted in red are compulsory.
- Proceed to fill in the id, name, version and optionally the description that you want to use for your experiment blueprint. Remember, you can only have one unique combination of the name and version.
- Once you are done filling in these fields, click “Next” to go to the VSB selection stage. An example of a filled-in experiment blueprint form is given in Figure 45.

Figure 45: 5GEVE Portal ASTI_UseCase Experiment Blueprint

- Click “Next” to move on to the VSB selection stage. In the VSB selection stage, using the “arrow” icon, select the site where you want to conduct the experiment, and thereafter, select the VSB that you want to use in that site. All your uploaded VSBs will be availed to you, and you can use the “arrow” icon to select the VSB that you want to use for this experiment. This process is illustrated further in Figure 46.

Figure 46: 5G-EVE Portal VSB Selection

Figure 47: 5G-EVE Portal VSB Selection

- An example of a selected site and VSB for the ASTI Use-Case is given in Figure 47.
- Click “Next” to move on to the Context Blueprint selection process.
- At this point, all the compatible context blueprints related to your VSB are available to you, and you have to select the context blueprint that you want to use for your experiment, as demonstrated in Figure 48. In this case, we selected both the delay and background traffic context blueprints.

Figure 48: 5G-EVE ASTI_USeCase CtxB Selection

- Click “Next” to move on to the NSD Onboarding stage. At this point, you have to upload the **composite NSD**. Bookmark not defined. we prepared in section A.3.1.3.
- So, click on “Choose file”, and select your “composite NSD” file that encompasses both your VSB and CtxB NSDs. With reference to Figure 49, at point 2, you will be able to view your onboarded composite NSD.

Figure 49: 5G EVE ASTI Use_Case Composite NSD Uploading

- Click “Next” to move on to the translation rules step. You will be presented with a page similar to Figure 50.
- In the translation rules section, the id and version of the uploaded composite NSD will have already been read by the portal.
- Next using the “arrow” icon, select the Network Service (NS) Deployment flavor and NS Instantiation Level id that you want to use in your experiment.
- Next, fill in the range of the parameters listed in both your VSB and context blueprints. Click on the “+” icon to add more parameters.

Figure 50: 5G EVE Composite NSD Translation rules

- An example of the composite NSD translation rules for the ASTI use-case is shown in Figure 51. The “*number_of_AGVs*” parameter is listed inside the parameters section of the ASTI VSB, the “*incoming_traffic_load*” parameter is listed inside the parameters section of the ASTI delay context blueprint, whereas the “*bg_traffic_rate*” is listed inside the parameters section of the ASTI background traffic context blueprint.

Figure 51: 5G EVE ASTI Composite NSD Translation Rules.

- Once done filling in all the required values, click “Next” to move on to the Metrics & KPIs section.
- In the Metrics & KPIs section, you have two parts i.e., Metrics and KPIs as illustrated in Figure 52. To understand what each of the parameters in the Metrics and KPIs parts means, please refer to Table 72.
- The Metrics requested at this stage are the same metrics listed in your context blueprints under the “*applicationMetrics*” section. When in doubt, please refer to the values you put in that section of the context blueprint.

Figure 52: 5G EVE Experiment Blueprint Metrics & KPIs Section

Table 72: 5G EVE Metrics & KPIs parameters

Part 1- Metrics		
Parameter Type	Description	Comments
Metric Type	Type of the metric you want to measure	Current possible values [LOST_PKT, RECEIVED_PKT, SENT_PKT, LATENCY, BANDWIDTH]
Interval	The time interval by which you want to measure your metric	Depends on the metric you are considering
Collection Type	Metric collection method	Current possible values [CUMULATIVE, DELTA, GAUGE]
Metric Id	Id of your metric	uuid format
Graph Type	Type of Graph to use to display the metric	Current possible values [LINE, PIE, COUNTER, GAUGE]
Name	Name of the metric	
Unit	Standard SI Unit in which the metric is to be measured	For time-related metrics, this could be “s” for seconds and “ms” for milliseconds
<i>To add more metrics, please click on the “+” icon</i>		

Part 2 – KPIs		
Parameter Type	Description	Comments
Formula	Formula/Equation to compute your KPIs	In case your KPI is as a result of applying some sort of operation(s)/formaula to the collected metrics. Otherwise, if your KPI is the same as the collected metric, then in that case just put the metric name as the formula.
Interval	Interval at which this KPI should be computed	Depends on the KPIs you are looking at
KPI Id	Id of your KPI	uuid format
Graph Type	Type of Graph to use to display the KPI	Current possible values [LINE, PIE, COUNTER, GAUGE]
Name	Name of the KPI	
Unit	Standard SI Unit of the KPI	For time related KPIs, this could be “s” for seconds and “ms” for milliseconds
Metric Ids	Ids of the metrics you want to consider for this KPI	Add all the metric ids of the metrics used for this KPI. These metrics should be related to the formula given above

To add more metrics, please click on the “+” icon

- An example of a filled-in Metrics & KPIs section for the ASTI Use-Case is given in Figure 53.

The screenshot shows a configuration interface for Metrics and KPIs. It is divided into three sections: Metrics, KPIs, and a bottom section with minus and plus icons.

- Metric 1:** Metric Type: LATENCY, Collection Type: GAUGE, Graph Type: LINE. Formula: `asti_agv_latency`. Unit: `ms`.
- Metric 2:** Metric Type: LOST_PKT, Collection Type: GAUGE, Graph Type: LINE. Formula: `asti_agv_lost_pkts`. Unit: `percentage`.
- KPI 1:** Formula: `asti_agv_latency`. Collection Type: GAUGE, Graph Type: LINE. Unit: `ms`.
- KPI 2:** Formula: `100 - (asti_agv_lost_pkts)`. Collection Type: GAUGE, Graph Type: LINE. Unit: `percentage`.

Figure 53: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Metrics & KPIs

- Click “Next” to move on to the “Test Cases” section.

- In the “Test Cases” section, please select one of the test-case blueprints that you created earlier (in section A.4.2.2) as shown in Figure 54.

Figure 54: 5G EVE ExpB Test Case Blueprint Selection

- Once done, please click on the “Submit” button to submit your completed experiment blueprint (ExpB) which contains your selected VSB, CtxB, TCB, composite NSD, KPIs and Infrastructure metrics.

A.4.3.1. Verification of the Experiment Blueprints submission

- After clicking the “submit” button, if your submission was successful, you will be presented with a message with the “**SUCCESS**” keyword in the body response.
- Otherwise, if your submission failed, you will be presented with an error response message with the “**FAILED**” keyword in the body response.
- In case your submission fails, please refer to section A.11 for some troubleshooting tips.
- In order to verify that your Experiment Blueprint was uploaded successfully, please click on the “**view**” tab of the Experiment Blueprints section. This is illustrated in Figure 55.

Figure 55: 5G EVE Experiment Blueprints View

- As you can see from Figure 55, our experiment is listed however to confirm that the submission was successful then we have to click on the eye icon.
- Clicking on the eye icon, we can see that we are able to view our experiment blueprint as shown in Figure 56.

Field	Value
Name	asti_agv_expb_27_05
Id	229
Version	1.0
Description	ASTI AGV experiment blueprint 27_05
KPIs	asti_agv_latency_kpi asti_agv_reliability_kpi
Metrics	asti_agv_latency asti_agv_lost_pkts
Compatible Sites	SPAIN_5TONIC
Vertical Service	ASTI AGV control and automation
Execution Contexts	ASTI Delay Component ASTI_CtxB_Bg_Traffic
Test Cases	asti_testcase_v2
Onboarded NSDs	af07cf75-5770-46c0-9f75-373a30877556

Figure 56: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Experiment Blueprint

- At this point, we are done with designing our experiment, hence we are ready to move on the next section i.e., Requesting an experiment.

A.4.4. MULTI-SITE COMPOSITE DESCRIPTORS DESIGN

- For multi-site experiments, the procedure for uploading the composite blueprints and NSDs is a little different.
- First of all, upload the VSBs for each constituent site involved in the multi-site experiment following the steps provided Section A.4.1; and thereafter, for each nested VSB upload, the experiment developer has to note down the Id as provided by the portal. An example of a nested VSB Id is indicated in Figure 57.

Id	Name	Version	Description	Configurable Parameters
774	Gaming Use Case Nested_ns_ES_v3	3.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Spain_v3	- Number of players
782	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Greece_v3	3.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming UC_v3	- Number of players
790	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v3	3.0	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v3	- Number of players - Number of players
862	Simple_VSB_with_Apache_02_03_diagnosis	6.0	Simple VSB - Apache instance and a delay generator	- Number of user equipments
879	Gaming Use Case Nested_ns_ES_v4	4.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Spain_v4	- Number of players
887	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming Use Case_Greece_v5	5.0	Blueprint for 5G EVE Multi-site Gaming UC_v5	- Number of players
895	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v4	4.0	Composite VSB for the Gaming multi-site UC_v4	- Number of players - Number of players - Number of players

Figure 57: Composite VSB_Nested VSB Id

- Upon finishing the nested VSB uploads and noting down their Ids, go ahead and update the composite VSB to reflect these nested VSB Ids as illustrated in Figure 58.

```

1 ---
2 interSite: true
3 version: '1.6'
4 name: Composite testing Service enhanced without radio_metrics
5 description: Composite VSB
6 parameters:
7 - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Spain
8   parameterName: Number of User Equipments
9   parameterType: number
10  parameterDescription: Number of web users_Spain
11    (Mandatory)
12  applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
13 - parameterId: No_Of_UEs_Italy
14   parameterName: Number of User Equipments
15   parameterType: number
16   parameterDescription: Number of web users_Italy
17    (Mandatory)
18  applicabilityField: Simple Use Case
19 atomicComponents:
20 - componentId: " apache"
21   serversNumber: 1
22   compatibleSite: SPAIN_5TONIC
23   type: SERVICE
24   associatedVsbId: '211'
25 - componentId: tracker_turin
26   serversNumber: 1
27   associatedVsbId: '260'
28   compatibleSite: ITALY_TURIN
29   type: SERVICE
30 applicationMetrics: []
31 endPoints:
32 - endPointId: cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
33   external: true
34   management: false
35   ranConnection: true
36 connectivityServices:
37 - endPointIds:
38   - cp_tracker_ext_in_composite
39   management: true
40   external: true
41   name: tracker_ext
42 compatibleSites:
43 - SPAIN_5TONIC
44 - ITALY_TURIN
  
```

Updated Nested VSB Ids after uploading all the nested VSBs to

Figure 58: Updating the Composite VSB before uploading

- After updating the composite VSB with the updated nested VSB Ids, go ahead and upload it to the platform following the steps presented in section A.4.1.
- Proceed to upload the composite TCB and create the Experiment blueprint following the steps presented in Sections A.4.2.2 and A.4.3, respectively.
- When done, proceed with the following sections to request, instantiate and execute your multi-site experiment.

A.5. 5G EVE PORTAL REQUEST EXPERIMENT

- In this section, we will cover the steps taken in order to request an experiment in the 5G EVE portal.
- Go back to the 5G EVE portal home page and this time, click on the “Request Experiments” tool as shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59: 5G EVE Portal Home Page

- After clicking on the “Request Experiments” section, you will be presented with a screen similar to the one shown in Figure 60.
- Inside the 5G EVE portal, you can request an experiment by using either the “**Experiment Descriptors create**” wizard or by using the “**Intent-based networking (IBN) experiment scheduling**” tool as illustrated in Figure 60.

Figure 60: 5G EVE Portal Request Experiments page

A.5.1. 5G EVE PORTAL CREATE EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTOR

- To request an experiment using the “Experiment Descriptors create” wizard, go ahead and click on the “*Experiment Descriptors Create*” icon. This wizard will guide you through the steps needed to create the various descriptors of your experiment i.e., Vertical Service, Context, Test-Case and Experiment Descriptors.
- Once inside the “*Experiment Descriptors Create*”, you will be presented with a form similar to Figure 61.
- So, go ahead and use the “arrow” icon to select the experiment blueprint associated to this experiment descriptor followed by the name and version.

Figure 61: 5G EVE Experiment Descriptor metadata page

- An example of the Experiment descriptor metadata for the ASTI use case that we have been using in this document is given in Figure 62.

Figure 62: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Experiment Descriptors Metadata

- Click “Next” to move on to the “VS Descriptors” section. The “VS Descriptors” page is displayed in Figure 63.

Figure 63: 5G EVE Vertical Service Descriptor page

- Inside the “*VS Descriptors*” section, please input the name and version you want to use for the Vertical Service Descriptor.
- The main difference between the Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD) and Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) is that the VSD is the parameterized version of your VSB, i.e. Inside the VSD, the actual values of the VSB parameters to be used in the experiment are provided.
- Inside the VSD, the VSB parameters are captured by the QoS parameters section. So, using the “arrow” icon, go ahead and select the VSB parameter to associate with your VSD.
- Next, we move on to the Slice Parameters selection. Please click on the “arrow” button, and you will be presented with the parameters shown in Table 73.

Table 73: 5G EVE VSD Slice Parameters Description

Slice Parameters		
Parameter	Possible Values	Description
Management_Type	Provider_Managed	This vertical service is to be managed by the 5G EVE system
	Tenant_Managed	This vertical service will be managed by the Vertical Service Provider
Slice_Service_Type	EMBB	Mobile Broadband use-cases
	URLLC	High bandwidth with ultra-low latency applications
	M_IOT	Massive Internet-of-devices

- Select the Management_Type and Slice_Service_Type that correspond to your use-case.
- Finally, check public if your experiment is publicly available to every user of the 5G EVE platform. Please refer to Figure 64 for the VSD of the ASTI use-case that we have been using in this document.

The “*number of AGVs*” is the parameter inside the ASTI VSB, so we select it and input the actual value that we want to use for this experiment. For the experiment, we want to use “*1*” AGV.

Figure 64: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case VSD parameters

- Click “Next” to move on to the “KPIs” section. As you can in Figure 65, the KPI that we added in the ASTI Experiment blueprint has already been selected for us. In this example, this KPI is ASTI_latency.

Figure 65: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case ExpD KPI

- Click “Next” to move on to the “Context Details” section. As you can see in Figure 66, the context associated with our Experiment blueprint has also already been selected for us.

Figure 66: 5G EVE ASTI ExpD Delay_Context

- By clicking on the “ASTI traffic Delay Generator Service”, the parameter(s) associated with your delay context blueprint will be presented to you and you have to select the actual value(s) of the parameter(s) that you want to use in this experiment. This is illustrated in Figure 67.

Figure 67: 5G EVE ASTI ExpD Delay_Context Parameter

- Click “Next” to go to the “Test Cases Configuration” section. As you can in Figure 68, our “ASTI delay test case” associated with this experiment blueprint is already available to us. So, go ahead and click on the “arrow” button to select our test case parameter values.

Figure 68: 5G EVE ExpD Test Cases Configuration

- For the ASTI Use-Case, the test cases configuration parameter(s) are detailed in Figure 69.

Figure 69: 5G EVE ASTI ExpD Delay Test Case Parameters

- Once done, click on the “Submit” button in order to submit your Experiment Descriptor.

A.5.1. Verification of the Experiment Descriptor submission

- In order to verify that your Experiment Descriptor was uploaded successfully, please click on the “view” tab of the Experiment Descriptors section. This is illustrated in Figure 70.

Figure 70: 5G EVE Experiment Descriptors View

- As you can see from Figure 70, our experiment is listed however to confirm that the submission was successful then we have to click on the eye icon.
- Clicking on the eye icon, we can see that we are able to view our descriptors as shown in Figure 71.

Figure 71: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Experiment Descriptor Details

- In case you can't view one or more of your Experiment Descriptor, please refer to section **A.11** for some trouble-shooting tips.
- Now we are ready to schedule our experiment with the 5G EVE portal.

A.6. 5G EVE INTENT-BASED NETWORKING (IBN) EXPERIMENT SCHEDULING TOOL

- To request an experiment using the IBN experiment scheduling tool, go ahead and click on the “Intent Declaration” icon as shown in Figure 72.

Figure 72: 5G EVE Request Experiment using The IBN Tool

- The IBN tool offers two modes of operation: intent-based selection and the guided selection.
- The intent-based section enables the user to write his intent using natural language, defining the desired service, sites, and relevant parameters to customize an experiment.
- The guided selection consists of a step-by-step wizard to set up and schedule the desired experiment.
- After clicking on the “Intent Declaration” icon, a login page as shown in Figure 73, appears as the user must enter his 5G-EVE credentials to authenticate using the Role-Based Access Control Interface (RBAC).

Figure 73: 5G EVE IBN RBAC page

- A logout button appears at the upper right corner to quickly log out and terminate the active session.
- After RBAC authorizes the user, the intent-based and guided selection tools become available.

A.6.1. Intent based selection

In this mode, the user is asked to fill in the blank field with his intent. An intent can contain the following ones:

- Information from the desired experiment's description, so that the most fitting experiment blueprint is found (i.e. experiment with ares2t);
- Information about the desired site following the keyword "in" (i.e. in Italy, in Turin, in Greece etc.);
- Information about the experiment date that the user desires in the dd/mm/yyyy format (i.e. 26/06/2020);
- Information about the experiment start time in the hh:mm 24h format (i.e. 16:45);
- Values for the service and context parameters using the "#" sign followed by the value;
- Information about the experiment duration in minutes using the "#" sign followed by the duration and the "duration" keyword (i.e., #30 duration).

Table 74: 5G EVE intent-based selection parameters

5G EVE Intent Parameters	Possible values
Experiment use-case	ares2t, asti, orange_v360, politico_smartcity and wings_utilities
5G EVE site	Turin (Italy), 5TONIC(Spain), Athens (Greece), Paris (France), Nice (France), Rennes (France)
Date(dd/mm/yyyy)	16/06/2020
Time (hh:mm 24h format)	18:50
vsb and context parameters (begin with '#')	#5 devices (vsb parameter) and #10 load (ctxb parameter)
Experiment duration in minutes (begin with '#')	#40 duration

- Therefore, a full intent that captures all these parameters can be as follows:
 “experiment with ares2t in turin on 16/06/2020 and time 18:50 with #5 devices and #10 load and #20 delay and #40 duration”
- This is illustrated further in Figure 74.

Figure 74: 5G EVE Intent Expression

- The input is analysed, and the optimal service and experiment blueprint pair is shown to the user along with the extracted site similar to Figure 75.

5G EVE

New Intent Guided Selection 5G-EVE project 5G-EVE use cases 5G-EVE Portal Help Logout

Please fill in the missing parameters:

Site: ITALY_TURIN
 Service blueprint: ARES2T Tracker service
 Experiment blueprint: Ares2T tracking experiment

Retry Guided

[ARES2T Tracker service] - service parameters

Number of tracked devices

[Delay Generator] - context parameters

Incoming Traffic Load

[TCB Ares2T Tracking with delay] - test case parameters

delay

delay variance

consecutive delay dependency percentage

Experiment descriptor details

Name:

Experiment details

Date

Day: 18 Month: 6 Year: 2020

Time

Hour: 18 Minute: 50

Duration

Minutes: 40

Submit

1 field(s) left

Figure 75: 5G EVE Intent based tool-Experiment blueprint and service parameters selection

- All the parameters and experiment date/time/duration values that were recovered from the user's input are displayed in case the user wants to edit any value.
- It is important to note that the description field of each experiment blueprint that is onboarded at the Catalogue is evaluated and the one that is more correlated with the user intent is chosen.
- If every field has the desired value, the user submits the form.
- An experiment descriptor is created with all the information and is onboarded at the Portal Catalogue.
- Finally, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) is notified about the desired experiment details and the scheduling takes place.

A.6.2. Guided Selection

- In this section, the user follows a step-by-step approach accompanied with useful messages in order to configure an experiment.
- Initially, the user selects the desired site(s) to run an experiment as shown in Figure 76.

Figure 76: 5G EVE Intent Guided selection-select site

- The services that are supported in the selected site are shown in Figure 77 and the user chooses the suitable one.

Figure 77: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- Available Services

- The experiments that contain the selected service are shown and the desired one must be chosen as illustrated in Figure 78.

Figure 78: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- select desired experiment

- All the vertical service and context blueprint parameters are displayed, and the user is asked to fill in the desired values as shown in Figure 79.

Figure 79: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- Select VSB and CtxB parameters

- All the test case parameters are displayed, per test case, and the user is asked to fill in the desired values as shown in Figure 80.
- If the user desires to exclude a test case, he/she may put the value "-" to a parameter of this test case.

Figure 80: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site- select test case parameters

- Finally, the date/time/duration parameters of the experiment are asked and if the input is valid the user can submit the form as shown in Figure 81.

Figure 81: 5G EVE IBN tool: Site-schedule experiment using the intent-based tool

- Once again, an experiment descriptor is created with all the information and is onboarded at the Portal Catalogue and the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) is notified about the desired experiment details and the scheduling takes place.

A.7. 5G EVE PORTAL SCHEDULE EXPERIMENT

- This option is only required for those who used the Experiment Descriptors create wizard to create their descriptors.
- For those who used the intent tool, the experiment was already scheduled using the intent tool when you selected the time, date and duration of your experiment.
- To schedule an experiment, click on the “*New Experiment Schedule*” section as shown in Figure 82.

Figure 82: 5G EVE Request Experiments page

- On clicking the “*New Experiment Schedule*”, you are directed to the “*Schedule a New Experiment*” page shown in Figure 83.

Figure 83: 5G EVE Schedule a New Experiment

- To schedule an experiment, input the experiment’s name and then select the Experiment Descriptor’s name that you want to use by using the “arrow” icon.
- Thereafter, select the 5G EVE “*target site*” where you want to carry out your experiment. This parameter corresponds to the value of the “*compatibleSites*” parameter inside the VSB.
- Then, please select the start and end date of your experiment.
- An example of a scheduled experiment for the ASTI Use-Case is illustrated in Figure 84.

The screenshot shows the '5G EVE Portal' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a user profile 'superusertest', a home icon, 'Descriptors', and a back arrow. Below this, the text 'Schedule a New Experiment' is displayed. The main form area contains several input fields: a text field with the value 'astl_delay_test_experiment', a dropdown menu for 'Experiment Descriptor' with the selected value 'ASTI AGV Experiment Blueprint', and another dropdown menu for 'Target Site' with the selected value 'SPAIN_STONIC'. Below these are two date pickers, one showing '4/17/2020' and the other '4/24/2020'. At the bottom of the form is a green 'Submit' button.

Figure 84: 5G EVE ASTI Use-Case Scheduled Experiment

- Finally, click the “Submit” button to schedule an experiment.

A.8. MANAGE EXPERIMENT

- To view your scheduled experiment, go back to the 5G EVE home page.
- Then click on the “*Manage experiment*” section as shown in Figure 85.

Figure 85: 5G EVE Manage Experiment Section

- Clicking on the “*Manage Experiment*” section, you will see your scheduled experiment as shown in Figure 86.

ID	Descriptor ID	Sites	Status	Execution Status
7		FRANCE_NICE,FRANCE_RENNES,GREECE_ATHENS,ITALY_TURIN,SPAIN_STONIC,FRANCE_PARIS	TERMINATED	🔄 🔍 🗑️
15	ticketing_descriptor	FRANCE_NICE,FRANCE_RENNES,GREECE_ATHENS,ITALY_TURIN,SPAIN_STONIC,FRANCE_PARIS	FAILED	🔍 🗑️
16	ticketing_descriptor	FRANCE_NICE,FRANCE_RENNES,GREECE_ATHENS,ITALY_TURIN,SPAIN_STONIC,FRANCE_PARIS	ACCEPTED	🔍
18		SPAIN_STONIC	SCHEDULING	🔍
11	ticketing_descriptor	ITALY_TURIN	TERMINATED	🔄 🔍 🗑️
19		SPAIN_STONIC	READY	📄 🔄 🔍
17		SPAIN_STONIC	ACCEPTED	🔍
20	ASTI AOV Experiment Blueprint	SPAIN_STONIC	SCHEDULING	🔍

Figure 86: 5G EVE Experiment List

- At this stage, the site managers of the selected 5G EVE site will receive a ticket with your experiment request.
- If all the required experiment resources are available at the selected 5G EVE site, and the timeline is not an issue, then your experiment will be accepted, otherwise it will be rejected with a reason for the rejection.
- Going forward, to be able to test the experiment execution process of the portal, we are going to use a simpler use case (client - webserver service) because the VNFs needed to execute the ASTI use case were not ready at the time of writing this user manual.

- Once an experiment is accepted by the site manager of the selected 5G EVE site, then the experiment status inside the 5G EVE portal will change from “*SCHEDULING*” to “*ACCEPTED*” as shown in Figure 87.

Figure 87: 5G EVE Experiment Accepted

- After an experiment is accepted on the portal, you have to wait for the experiment status to change to “*READY*” before you can be able to execute your experiment on the platform. In some vertical services, the site managers might need to do some manual configurations to prepare the 5G EVE sites for the experiment execution.
- Once the experiment status changes to ready, as shown in Figure 88. Then, we are prepared to execute our experiment on the platform.

Figure 88: 5G EVE Experiment Ready

A.9. DEPLOY AND EXECUTE EXPERIMENT

- To execute an experiment on the 5G EVE platform, click on the icon indicated by the blue arrow in Figure 89.
- Upon clicking on that icon, you will be presented with a screen similar to Figure 89. Select “DEPLOY” and after click “Submit” to execute your experiment.

Figure 89: 5G EVE Execute an Experiment

- On submission, the experiment will start executing on the portal, and the experiment status will change to “INSTANTIATING” as indicated in Figure 90.

Figure 90: 5G EVE Experiment Instantiating

- Once the platform completes instantiating the experiment, the experiment status will change to “INSTANTIATED” as shown in Figure 91 or “FAILED” in case the instantiation has failed for whatever reason.

Figure 91: 5G EVE Instantiated Experiment

- To start executing tests on the instantiated experiment, click on the icon indicated by the blue arrow in Figure 91.
- On clicking on that icon, you will be presented by two options i.e., “EXECUTE” or “TERMINATE” as shown in Figure 92.

Figure 92: 5G EVE Execute Experiment

- Select “EXECUTE” to start executing the test cases associated with your experiment. After selecting “EXECUTE”, you will be asked to input the name of your execution, so input the name of your execution and after click submit to start running your tests.
- When the experiment is executing, the experiment status will change to “EXECUTING” as indicated in Figure 93.

Figure 93: 5G EVE Experiment Execution Running

A.10. 5G EVE PORTAL MONITORING & KPI REPORTING TOOLS

- As the experiment is running, you can view the monitoring metrics and 5G KPIs that you set in your context and experiment blueprints by clicking on the icon indicated by the blue arrow in Figure 93.
- For the simple Apache use case, the metrics and KPI graphs examples are given in Figure 94.

Figure 94: 5G EVE Simple Apache Use case KPI And Metrics Graphs

- Once the experiment has finished executing, the status will change from “*RUNNING EXECUTION*” back to “*INSTANTIATED*”. To view the experiment tests details, click on “eye” icon as indicated in Figure 95.

Figure 95: 5G EVE View Experiment Tests Report

- On clicking the “eye” icon, you will be presented with some summary statistics about your experiment as shown in Figure 96.

Figure 96: 5G EVE Experiment Tests Summary

- To view the 5G EVE KPIs validation report for the tests carried out in your experiment, please click on the “Report” icon as shown in Figure 96. Clicking on this icon, for this simple use case, the validation report looks similar to the one indicated in Figure 97.

Figure 97: 5G EVE KPI Validation Report

- As you can see in Figure 97, the validated KPI, i.e., *requests_time_taken_kpi*, is the KPI that you set when creating the experiment blueprint.
- And we can see that the KPI validation failed because we set the upper threshold (i.e., time taken by the requests KPI) to 40ms (refer to Figure 98), and yet the average time per request was **35.2ms** as indicated in Figure 97.


```
"refresh_token":
gOiAiSldÜIiwia2lkiA6ICI1YTc1MDk5OC04NjQ2LTQwODI-
tODhhMS1iZDg2NmQyZGZiYzcfQ..... ",
"username": "abc@abc.com"
}
```

"eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCI-

- Next, we shall proceed to obtain the experiment ID.

A.10.1.2. Obtain the Experiment ID

- In order to obtain the experiment ID, we have to interact with the REST API of the 5G EVE Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) component [1].
- So, by using the access token obtained from section A.10.1.1 above, we can make the following request to the ELM component to obtain the experiment id associated with our experiment descriptor id. The experiment descriptor id can be obtained from the portal, as illustrated in Figure 99.

Figure 99: Obtain the Experiment Descriptor ID from the 5G EVE portal

- For example, to obtain the experiment ID for the experiment descriptor ID “3137” highlighted in Figure 99 above, we can make a request similar to this:

```
curl --location --request GET 'https://portal.5g-eve.eu/portal/elm/experiment?experimentDescriptorId=3137' \
--header 'Authorization: Bearer eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCI-
gOiAiSldUIiwia2lkiA6ICJQS1Q1Q3Y3cVNwejIyYUJ1TXJmQVhNWVdBcUJfNkplaFlncEILR3V5VkM0In0 ' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--header 'Cookie: JSESSIONID=CB9F5DDEC96AAE9CBBFE80EEE9414F1F' \
--data-raw '{
"email": "abc@abc.com",
"password": "xyzzzz"
}'
```

Note: the authentication token has been truncated here for readability's sake

- If the request is successful, the experimenter will be presented with all the experiment details associated with that experiment descriptor ID. For the sake of readability, we shall only present here the first part of the response.

```
{
  "experimentId": "e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7",
  "name": "test_prod_exp_v2",
  "status": "INSTANTIATED",
  "experimentDescriptorId": "3137",
  "openTicketIds": [
    "403"
  ],
  "targetSites": [
    "SPAIN_5TONIC"
  ],
  "timeslot": {
    "startTime": "2021-03-19T00:00:00+01:00",
    "stopTime": "2021-03-20T23:59:59.999+01:00"
  }
}
```

- We can extract the experiment ID from this response, and now we are ready to retrieve the topics associated with this experiment with id “e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7”.

A.10.1.3. Retrieve Metrics and KPI Data

- To retrieve the metrics and KPI data associated with a particular experiment, we have to interact with the 5G EVE DCS component API to obtain the topics associated with the experiment and consequently retrieve the data published in a particular topic.
- For example, to retrieve the topics associated with the experiment presented in section A.10.1.2, we can make a request similar to this by specifying the experiment ID in the request

```
curl --location --request GET 'https://portal.5g-eve.eu/portal/dcs/topics/e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7' \
--header 'Authorization: Bearer eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IiJpYyYUJ1TXJmQVh' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--header 'Cookie: JSESSIONID=19B575C23684DE1A8827D47B8B73E577' \
--data-raw '{
  "email": "abc@abc.com",
  "password": "xyzxzzz"
}'
```

Note: the authentication token has been truncated here for readability's sake

- If the request is successful, then you will be presented with a list of topics associated to the experiment. For this experiment we only have one topic i.e., test_prod_v2.e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7.spain_5tonic.application_metric.apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken
- Finally, we can retrieve either the metrics or the KPI data published to a particular topic by specifying the topic id in the request, something similar to the request below.

```
curl --location --request GET 'https://portal.5g-eve.eu/portal/dcs/topics/e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7/test_prod_v2.e8660e91-75d0-411e-9831-ff193c62b7a7.spain_5tonic.application_metric.apache_client_vnf_requests_time_taken' \  
--header 'Authorization: Bearer eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6GoiAiSldUiwia2lkLiA6ICJQS1Q1Q3Y3cVNwejlYUj1TXJmQVh' \  
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \  
--header 'Cookie: JSESSIONID=19B575C23684DE1A8827D47B8B73E577' \  
--data-raw '{  
  "email": "superusertest@mail.com",  
  "password": "123456"  
}'
```

Note: the authentication token has been truncated here for readability's sake

- If the request is successful, then you will be able to view all the metric data that is currently published in that topic.

A.11. TROUBLE-SHOOTING TIPS

In this section, we present some tips to help you troubleshoot in case you run into some issues when designing, deploying, and executing your experiments on the 5G EVE platform:

A.11.1. COMMON GUIDELINES

- Make sure you have converted all YAML descriptor files to JSON before uploading.
- Each blueprint needs to have a corresponding NSD in IFA14 format.
- Ensure that all the blueprint and nsd ids are in UUID format.
- Make sure that your nsd descriptor files begin with the “*nsd_content*” parameter.
- For all the descriptors, use the experiment descriptor wizard on the 5G EVE portal to help you create the vertical service, context, test-case and experimental descriptors by inputting each of the parameters’ the exact values listed in the blueprints.

A.11.2. ISSUES SUBMITTING YOUR BLUEPRINTS

- Currently, the portal has integrated the “blueprint validator tool” that will be able to capture most of errors associated with submission of your blueprints and readily avail them.

A.11.3. ISSUES VIEWING YOUR BLUEPRINTS

- In this case, the issue is most probably related to your uploaded Blueprint.
- Always use the eye icon to check if your descriptors have been appropriately loaded. If you can’t view your descriptor, there may be something missing /wrongly filled in your Blueprint. However, if this the case, the “blueprint validator tool” will inform you of the error during blueprint upload.
- Watch out for the name and version of each Blueprint you upload. There can only be one name and version match.
- Inside the VSB blueprint, please ensure that the “*compatibleContextBlueprint*” parameter has UUIDs instead of the context blueprint names.
- For the Experiment Blueprint, use the portal to guide you.

A.11.4. SUBMISSION OF A TICKET TO THE 5G EVE PORTAL

- If none of the above troubleshooting tips work for you or your issue is not related to any of the above issues, then, in that case, you can submit a ticket to the 5G EVE portal by clicking on the “tickets” section anywhere you are on the portal as illustrated in Figure 100Figure 100.

Figure 100: 5G EVE Submit Ticket

- As you can see from Figure 100, no matter where you are on the portal, you can just click on “Tickets” to submit a ticket or report a bug on the portal.
- On clicking on “tickets,” you will be presented with a page similar to the one in Figure 101. Click on the “+” icon to create a new ticket, as indicated in Figure 101.

id	Product	Component	Status	Summary	Actions
282	SPAIN_STONIC	EXPERIMENT_SCHEDULE	CONFIRMED	apache_exec_27_05 SLOT_REQUEST	[edit] [delete]
281	5G-EVE_PORTAL	AUTHENTICATION	CONFIRMED	Testeando desde GUI	[edit] [delete]
280	5G-EVE_PORTAL	AUTHENTICATION	CONFIRMED	testing exp_dev tickets	[edit] [delete]
279	5G-EVE_PORTAL	AUTHENTICATION	CONFIRMED	Ticket from gui	[edit] [delete]
271	SPAIN_STONIC	EXPERIMENT_SCHEDULE	CONFIRMED	Test SLOT_REQUEST	[edit] [delete]
270	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing from gui correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
269	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing from gui correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
268	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File with space correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
267	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]
266	5G-EVE_PORTAL	VNF_UPLOADS	CONFIRMED	File testing correctly uploaded	[edit] [delete]

Figure 101: 5G EVE Tickets Page

- On clicking on the “+” icon, you will be presented with a page similar to Figure 102, so go ahead and select the 5G EVE product and component where you got the error by using the “arrow” buttons as shown in Figure 102. Provide a summary & description of your problem and select the admin user to assign the ticket to. Once done, click on “Create,” and an email will be sent to the assigned admin user, and your ticket will be handled as soon as possible.

Figure 102: 5G EVE Create New Ticket

- An example of a filled-in ticket is given in Figure 103.

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for creating a new ticket. The title is "Add new ticket". The form contains the following fields:

- Select a Product ***: 5G-EVE_PORTAL
- Select a Component ***: AUTHENTICATION
- Summary ***: Can't register
- Description ***: I tried to register and failed
- Select and admin user to assign the ticket**: ticketing@5g-eve.eu

A "Create" button is located at the bottom of the form.

Figure 103: 5G EVE Filed Ticket

- Once you are done filing your ticket, you can confirm that your ticket has been successfully created by looking at the new list of tickets and your ticket should be there.